

Dawn VIR Sequence report for Vesta Science Approach (VSA) (vir_da004)

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ABSTRACT

This document constitutes the official flight operation report for the VIR (Visible and Infrared Mapping Spectrometer) instrument onboard the Dawn spacecraft, specifically covering the commanding and sequencing activities performed for the vir_da004 session. These operations were executed as part of the VSA phase.

The mission profile focused on the observational sequences for the characterization of the planetary body Vesta, aiming to map its mineralogical features and surface properties.

The report details the generation of the instrument's commanding sequences and the formal verification process. All sequences have been checked against the mission's flight and guideline rules within the SASF (Spacecraft Activity Sequence File) framework. Furthermore, the VIR SASF files were successfully integrated with the sequences of the other onboard instruments to ensure system-level compatibility and resource management. The final integrated sequences were successfully uploaded and executed on the spacecraft during the scheduled vir_da004 window.

KEYWORDS

VIR • Spectral Instrument • Dawn NASA Mission

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References

- [1] M. de Sanctis *et al.*, "The VIR Spectrometer," *issr*, vol. 163, no. 1-4, pp. 329-369, Dec. 2011, doi: 10.1007/s11214-010-9668-5.
- [2] A. K. J. Stipanuk, "Spacecraft Activity Sequence File (SASF) Interface.," *Deep Space Mission System (DSMS) Subsystem Software Interface Specification*, 2004.

1. Check list of the sequence vir_vsa_OpNav_017.r01.sasf

The following table presents the checklist of the validation tests performed on the vir_vsa_OpNav_017.r01.sasf sequence. The OK column indicates successful test execution, while the NA (Not Applicable) column denotes tests that are not relevant to this specific sequence. The P (Pending) column identifies tests that have failed or require further resolution. The Item column serves as a unique identifier for each performed test, and the Description column provides a concise summary of the specific verification criteria.

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
Flight Rules				
✓	□	□	F-VIRC09	VIR cryocooler cool down time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC10	VIR cover actuation time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC11	Allow enough time for VIR to transition to STAND_BY after a SCIENCE mode
□	✓	□	F-VIRC12	Allow enough time for VIR to STAND_BY after issuing VIR_MM_DUMP command
✓	□	□	F-VIRA16	VIR timing requirements for repetition time and integration time
Guideline				
Syntax and grammar analysis				
✓	□	□	G-VIRO1	Syntax and grammar analysis
✓	□	□	G-VIRO2	File name and revision number
✓	□	□	G-VIRO3	The execution of the sequence occurs within the time boundaries (APPLICABLE-(START&STOP)-TIME)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO4	BEGIN and CUTOFF are equal to boundaries
□	✓	□	G-VIRO5	Required of VML_START
□	✓	□	G-VIRO6	if VML_START, file buffer loaded (d:/fb05)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO7	Numerical parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO8	String parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO9	Integration time and delay time are such that the two channels window timing are centered
✓	□	□	G-VIR10	Do not use epochs_labels different from those defined in EPOCH_DEF
Running and simulating of the sequence				
✓	□	□	G-VIR11	No duplicates found in the list of requests names
✓	□	□	G-VIR12	VIR Mode transition
□	✓	□	G-VIR13	All VIR command have time for execution
□	□	✓	G-VIR14	There are partial dumps
□	□	✓	G-VIR15	No time overlap between the requests
✓	□	□	G-VIR16	Cover open during Science acquisition
□	✓	□	G-VIR17	There are critical commands accepted
□	✓	□	G-VIR18	Cryocooler used only when need
□	✓	□	G-VIR19	When using VIR_SAFE or VIR_TC_MM_CONF is required the Mass Memory to have all pages empty
✓	□	□	G-VIR20	Avoid MM overflow

1.1 List of operations

The following table details the operational operations executed within the vir_vsa_OpNav_017.r01.sasf sequence. For each operation, the start time, stop time, and duration (expressed in seconds) are reported.

Request Name	Start Time[s]	Stop Time[s]	Duration[s]
VIR_VSA_PowerOn_017	364134240	364134661	421
VIR_VSA_CryocoolerOn_017	364134840	364145641	10801
VIR_VSA_OpenCover_017	364145640	364145701	61
VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017	364145761	364150118	4357
VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017	364150141	364152866	2725
VIR_VSA_CloseCover_017	364152866	364152927	61
VIR_VSA_CryocoolerOff_017	364152926	364152933	7
VIR_VSA_DumpDataToVR4_017	364176600	364178401	1801
VIR_VSA_PowerOff_017	364178520	-864426279	-1228604799

1.2 Memories usage

Ecco la traduzione in inglese tecnico-scientifico, ottimizzata per la descrizione di grafici di telemetria e occupazione dati:

Technical English Translation The following plots illustrate the data volume and memory occupancy for both the VIR infrared (IR) and visible (VIS) channels. The transitions between the various instrument operational modes are indicated by the green vertical lines.

2. Check list of the sequence vir_vsa_OpNav_018.r07.sasf

The following table presents the checklist of the validation tests performed on the vir_vsa_OpNav_018.r07.sasf sequence. The OK column indicates successful test execution, while the NA (Not Applicable) column denotes tests that are not relevant to this specific sequence. The P (Pending) column identifies tests that have failed or require further resolution. The Item column serves as a unique identifier for each performed test, and the Description column provides a concise summary of the specific verification criteria.

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
Flight Rules				
✓	□	□	F-VIRC09	VIR cryocooler cool down time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC10	VIR cover actuation time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC11	Allow enough time for VIR to transition to STAND_BY after a SCIENCE mode
□	✓	□	F-VIRC12	Allow enough time for VIR to STAND_BY after issuing VIR_MM_DUMP command
✓	□	□	F-VIRA16	VIR timing requirements for repetition time and integration time
Guideline				
Syntax and grammar analysis				
✓	□	□	G-VIRO1	Syntax and grammar analysis
✓	□	□	G-VIRO2	File name and revision number
✓	□	□	G-VIRO3	The execution of the sequence occurs within the time boundaries (APPLICABLE-(START&STOP)-TIME)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO4	BEGIN and CUTOFF are equal to boundaries
□	✓	□	G-VIRO5	Required of VML_START
□	✓	□	G-VIRO6	if VML_START, file buffer loaded (d:/fb05)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO7	Numerical parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO8	String parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO9	Integration time and delay time are such that the two channels window timing are centered
✓	□	□	G-VIR10	Do not use epochs_labels different from those defined in EPOCH_DEF
Running and simulating of the sequence				
✓	□	□	G-VIR11	No duplicates found in the list of requests names
✓	□	□	G-VIR12	VIR Mode transition
□	✓	□	G-VIR13	All VIR command have time for execution
□	□	✓	G-VIR14	There are partial dumps
□	□	✓	G-VIR15	No time overlap between the requests
✓	□	□	G-VIR16	Cover open during Science acquisition
□	✓	□	G-VIR17	There are critical commands accepted
□	✓	□	G-VIR18	Cryocooler used only when need
□	✓	□	G-VIR19	When using VIR_SAFE or VIR_TC_MM_CONF is required the Mass Memory to have all pages empty
✓	□	□	G-VIR20	Avoid MM overflow

2.1 List of operations

The following table details the operational operations executed within the vir_vsa_OpNav_018.r07.sasf sequence. For each operation, the start time, stop time, and duration (expressed in seconds) are reported.

Request Name	Start Time[s]	Stop Time[s]	Duration[s]
VIR_VSA_PowerOn_018	364278960	364279381	421
VIR_VSA_FullCalibration_018	364279560	364292177	12617
VIR_VSA_OpenCover_018	364293240	364293301	61
VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_018a	364293390	364296457	3067
VIR_VSA_DumpDataToVR4_018a	364296460	364297301	841
VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_018b	364297300	364300367	3067
VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_018c	364300366	364301125	759
VIR_VSA_CloseCover_018	364301221	364301282	61
VIR_VSA_CryocoolerOff_018	364301281	364301288	7
VIR_VSA_DumpDataToVR4_018b	364319040	364325641	6601
VIR_VSA_PowerOff_018	364325640	-625360087	-989685727

2.2 Memories usage

Ecco la traduzione in inglese tecnico-scientifico, ottimizzata per la descrizione di grafici di telemetria e occupazione dati:

Technical English Translation The following plots illustrate the data volume and memory occupancy for both the VIR infrared (IR) and visible (VIS) channels. The transitions between the various instrument operational modes are indicated by the green vertical lines.

3. Check list of the sequence vir_vsa_OpNav_019.r06.sasf

The following table presents the checklist of the validation tests performed on the vir_vsa_OpNav_019.r06.sasf sequence. The OK column indicates successful test execution, while the NA (Not Applicable) column denotes tests that are not relevant to this specific sequence. The P (Pending) column identifies tests that have failed or require further resolution. The Item column serves as a unique identifier for each performed test, and the Description column provides a concise summary of the specific verification criteria.

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
Flight Rules				
✓	□	□	F-VIRC09	VIR cryocooler cool down time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC10	VIR cover actuation time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC11	Allow enough time for VIR to transition to STAND_BY after a SCIENCE mode
□	✓	□	F-VIRC12	Allow enough time for VIR to STAND_BY after issuing VIR_MM_DUMP command
✓	□	□	F-VIRA16	VIR timing requirements for repetition time and integration time
Guideline				
Syntax and grammar analysis				
✓	□	□	G-VIRO1	Syntax and grammar analysis
✓	□	□	G-VIRO2	File name and revision number
✓	□	□	G-VIRO3	The execution of the sequence occurs within the time boundaries (APPLICABLE-(START&STOP)-TIME)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO4	BEGIN and CUTOFF are equal to boundaries
□	✓	□	G-VIRO5	Required of VML_START
□	✓	□	G-VIRO6	if VML_START, file buffer loaded (d:/fb05)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO7	Numerical parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO8	String parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO9	Integration time and delay time are such that the two channels window timing are centered
✓	□	□	G-VIR10	Do not use epochs_labels different from those defined in EPOCH_DEF
Running and simulating of the sequence				
✓	□	□	G-VIR11	No duplicates found in the list of requests names
✓	□	□	G-VIR12	VIR Mode transition
□	✓	□	G-VIR13	All VIR command have time for execution
□	□	✓	G-VIR14	There are partial dumps
□	□	✓	G-VIR15	No time overlap between the requests
✓	□	□	G-VIR16	Cover open during Science acquisition
□	✓	□	G-VIR17	There are critical commands accepted
□	✓	□	G-VIR18	Cryocooler used only when need
□	✓	□	G-VIR19	When using VIR_SAFE or VIR_TC_MM_CONF is required the Mass Memory to have all pages empty
✓	□	□	G-VIR20	Avoid MM overflow

3.1 List of operations

The following table details the operational operations executed within the vir_vsa_OpNav_019.r06.sasf sequence. For each operation, the start time, stop time, and duration (expressed in seconds) are reported.

Request Name	Start Time[s]	Stop Time[s]	Duration[s]
VIR_VSA_PowerOn_019	364706880	364707301	421
VIR_VSA_FullCalibration_019	364707480	364720097	12617
VIR_VSA_OpenCover_019	364720380	364720441	61
VIR_VSA_CubeToMM2VR4_019	364720530	364726961	6431
VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_019	364726960	364731392	4432
VIR_VSA_CloseCover_019	364731391	364731452	61
VIR_VSA_DumpDataToVR4_019	364742700	364751101	8401

3.2 Memories usage

Ecco la traduzione in inglese tecnico-scientifico, ottimizzata per la descrizione di grafici di telemetria e occupazione dati:

Technical English Translation The following plots illustrate the data volume and memory occupancy for both the VIR infrared (IR) and visible (VIS) channels. The transitions between the various instrument operational modes are indicated by the green vertical lines.

4. Check list of the sequence vir_vsa_RC_003a.r08.sasf

The following table presents the checklist of the validation tests performed on the vir_vsa_RC_003a.r08.sasf sequence. The OK column indicates successful test execution, while the NA (Not Applicable) column denotes tests that are not relevant to this specific sequence. The P (Pending) column identifies tests that have failed or require further resolution. The Item column serves as a unique identifier for each performed test, and the Description column provides a concise summary of the specific verification criteria.

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
Flight Rules				
✓	□	□	F-VIRC09	VIR cryocooler cool down time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC10	VIR cover actuation time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC11	Allow enough time for VIR to transition to STAND_BY after a SCIENCE mode
□	✓	□	F-VIRC12	Allow enough time for VIR to STAND_BY after issuing VIR_MM_DUMP command
✓	□	□	F-VIRA16	VIR timing requirements for repetition time and integration time
Guideline				
Syntax and grammar analysis				
✓	□	□	G-VIRO1	Syntax and grammar analysis
✓	□	□	G-VIRO2	File name and revision number
✓	□	□	G-VIRO3	The execution of the sequence occurs within the time boundaries (APPLICABLE-(START&STOP)-TIME)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO4	BEGIN and CUTOFF are equal to boundaries
□	✓	□	G-VIRO5	Required of VML_START
□	✓	□	G-VIRO6	if VML_START, file buffer loaded (d:/fb05)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO7	Numerical parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO8	String parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO9	Integration time and delay time are such that the two channels window timing are centered
✓	□	□	G-VIR10	Do not use epochs_labels different from those defined in EPOCH_DEF
Running and simulating of the sequence				
✓	□	□	G-VIR11	No duplicates found in the list of requests names
✓	□	□	G-VIR12	VIR Mode transition
□	✓	□	G-VIR13	All VIR command have time for execution
□	□	✓	G-VIR14	There are partial dumps
□	□	✓	G-VIR15	No time overlap between the requests
✓	□	□	G-VIR16	Cover open during Science acquisition
□	✓	□	G-VIR17	There are critical commands accepted
□	✓	□	G-VIR18	Cryocooler used only when need
□	✓	□	G-VIR19	When using VIR_SAFE or VIR_TC_MM_CONF is required the Mass Memory to have all pages empty
✓	□	□	G-VIR20	Avoid MM overflow

4.1 List of operations

The following table details the operational operations executed within the vir_vsa_RC_003a.r08.sasf sequence. For each operation, the start time, stop time, and duration (expressed in seconds) are reported.

Request Name	Start Time[s]	Stop Time[s]	Duration[s]
VIR_VSA_RC3FullCalibNoCooling_001	364759200	364761017	1817
VIR_VSA_RC3OpenCover_001	364761780	364761841	61
VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToMM2VR4_001	364761930	364768442	6512
VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_002	364769430	364773238	3808
VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_003	364776930	364780738	3808
VIR_VSA_RC3CloseCover_001	364781430	364781491	61
VIR_VSA_RC3CryocoolerOff_001	364781490	364781497	7
VIR_VSA_RC3DumpDataToVR4_002	364791900	364801501	9601

4.2 Memories usage

Ecco la traduzione in inglese tecnico-scientifico, ottimizzata per la descrizione di grafici di telemetria e occupazione dati:

Technical English Translation The following plots illustrate the data volume and memory occupancy for both the VIR infrared (IR) and visible (VIS) channels. The transitions between the various instrument operational modes are indicated by the green vertical lines.

5. Check list of the sequence vir_vsa_RC_003b.r06.sasf

The following table presents the checklist of the validation tests performed on the vir_vsa_RC_003b.r06.sasf sequence. The OK column indicates successful test execution, while the NA (Not Applicable) column denotes tests that are not relevant to this specific sequence. The P (Pending) column identifies tests that have failed or require further resolution. The Item column serves as a unique identifier for each performed test, and the Description column provides a concise summary of the specific verification criteria.

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
Flight Rules				
✓	□	□	F-VIRC09	VIR cryocooler cool down time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC10	VIR cover actuation time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC11	Allow enough time for VIR to transition to STAND_BY after a SCIENCE mode
□	✓	□	F-VIRC12	Allow enough time for VIR to STAND_BY after issuing VIR_MM_DUMP command
✓	□	□	F-VIRA16	VIR timing requirements for repetition time and integration time
Guideline				
Syntax and grammar analysis				
✓	□	□	G-VIRO1	Syntax and grammar analysis
✓	□	□	G-VIRO2	File name and revision number
✓	□	□	G-VIRO3	The execution of the sequence occurs within the time boundaries (APPLICABLE-(START&STOP)-TIME)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO4	BEGIN and CUTOFF are equal to boundaries
□	✓	□	G-VIRO5	Required of VML_START
□	✓	□	G-VIRO6	if VML_START, file buffer loaded (d:/fb05)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO7	Numerical parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO8	String parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO9	Integration time and delay time are such that the two channels window timing are centered
✓	□	□	G-VIR10	Do not use epochs_labels different from those defined in EPOCH_DEF
Running and simulating of the sequence				
✓	□	□	G-VIR11	No duplicates found in the list of requests names
✓	□	□	G-VIR12	VIR Mode transition
□	✓	□	G-VIR13	All VIR command have time for execution
□	□	✓	G-VIR14	There are partial dumps
□	□	✓	G-VIR15	No time overlap between the requests
✓	□	□	G-VIR16	Cover open during Science acquisition
✓	□	□	G-VIR17	There are critical commands accepted
□	✓	□	G-VIR18	Cryocooler used only when need
✓	□	□	G-VIR19	When using VIR_SAFE or VIR_TC_MM_CONF is required the Mass Memory to have all pages empty
✓	□	□	G-VIR20	Avoid MM overflow

5.1 List of operations

The following table details the operational operations executed within the vir_vsa_RC_003b.r06.sasf sequence. For each operation, the start time, stop time, and duration (expressed in seconds) are reported.

Request Name	Start Time[s]	Stop Time[s]	Duration[s]
VIR_VSA_RC3bFullCalibration_001	364801500	364814117	12617
VIR_VSA_RC3bConfigMemory6Gb_001	364814341	364814353	12
VIR_VSA_RC3bOpenCover_001	364814400	364814461	61
VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_001	364814460	364817528	3068
VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_002	364817790	364820858	3068
VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_003	364821120	364824188	3068
VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_004	364824450	364827518	3068
VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_005	364827780	364830848	3068
VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_006	364831110	364834178	3068
VIR_VSA_RC3bCloseCover_001	364834440	364834501	61
VIR_VSA_RC3bCryocoolerOff_001	364834500	364834507	7
VIR_VSA_RC3bDumpDataToVR4_001	364834560	364836961	2401
VIR_VSA_RC3bDumpDataToVR4_002	364857600	364863001	5401
VIR_VSA_RC3bDumpDataToVR4_003	364864800	364870201	5401
VIR_VSA_RC3bDumpDataToVR4_004	364872000	364877401	5401
VIR_VSA_RC3bDumpDataToVR4_005	364879200	364888201	9001
VIR_VSA_RC3bPowerOff_001	364888500	1082562901	717674401

5.2 Memories usage

Ecco la traduzione in inglese tecnico-scientifico, ottimizzata per la descrizione di grafici di telemetria e occupazione dati:

Technical English Translation The following plots illustrate the data volume and memory occupancy for both the VIR infrared (IR) and visible (VIS) channels. The transitions between the various instrument operational modes are indicated by the green vertical lines.

6. Integrated sequence: da004c.02.filter.rsoe

The following table presents the checklist of the validation tests performed on the da004c.02.filter.rsoe sequence. The OK column indicates successful test execution, while the NA (Not Applicable) column denotes tests that are not relevant to this specific sequence. The P (Pending) column identifies tests that have failed or require further resolution. The Item column serves as a unique identifier for each performed test, and the Description column provides a concise summary of the specific verification criteria.

The VIR instrument was configured to acquire 6 calibration cubes and 77 cubes for IR channel and 77 for VIS channel.

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
Flight Rules				
✓	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	F-VIRC09	VIR cryocooler cool down time
✓	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	F-VIRC10	VIR cover actuation time
✓	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	F-VIRC11	Allow enough time for VIR to transition to STAND_BY after a SCIENCE mode
✓	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	F-VIRC12	Allow enough time for VIR to STAND_BY after issuing VIR_MM_DUMP command
✓	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	F-VIRA16	VIR timing requirements for repetition time and integration time
Guideline				
Running and simulating of the sequence				
✓	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIR12	VIR Mode transition
✓	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIR13	All VIR command have time for execution
✓	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIR14	There are partial dumps
✓	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIR15	No time overlap between the requests
✓	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIR16	Cover open during Science acquisition
✓	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIR17	There are critical commands accepted
✓	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIR18	Cryocooler used only when need

7. Appendix

This appendix contains the SASF (Spacecraft Activity Sequence File) sequences referenced in this report, along with the SPICE meta-kernel employed for the geometric computations and reference frame transformations.

The following SASF files were processed:

7.1 The sequence: vir_vsa_OpNav_017.r01.sasf

1	CCSD3ZF0000100000001NJPL3KS0L015\$MARK\$;	sasf
2	MISSION_NAME = DAWN;	
3	SPACECRAFT_NAME = DAWN;	
4	DATA_SET_ID = SPACECRAFT_ACTIVITY_SEQUENCE_DSC;	
5	FILE_NAME = vir_vsa_OpNav_017.r01.sasf;	
6	APPLICABLE_START_TIME = 2011-197T17:03:00.000;	
7	APPLICABLE_STOP_TIME = 2011-206T00:00:00.000;	
8	PRODUCT_CREATION_TIME = 2011-147T13:06:09.000;	
9	PRODUCER_ID = VIRTEAM;	
10	SEQ_ID = vir_vsa_OpNav_017.r01;	
11	HOST_ID = dawndsc2;	
12	CCSD3RE00000\$MARK\$NJPL3IF0M01300000001;	
13	\$\$DWN SPACECRAFT ACTIVITY SEQUENCE FILE	
14	*****	
15	*PROJECT DWN	
16	*SPACECRAFT 203	
17	*OPERATOR sfonte	
18	*FILE_CMPLT TRUE	
19	*DATE Fri May 27 13:06:09 2011	
20	*SEQGEN V29.5.2 Thu Nov 29 13:34:23 PST 2007	
21	*BEGIN 2011-197T17:03:00.000	
22	*CUTOFF 2011-206T00:00:00.000	
23	*TITLE VSA_OpNav_014_da004_VIR_shutter_test	
24	*EPOCHS_DEF	
25	*VSA_OPNAV_017, 2011-198T03:36:00.000	
26	*EPOCHS_END	
27	*Input files used:	

28	*File Type	Last modified	File name
29	*****		
30	\$\$EOH		
31	\$\$EOD		
32	request(VIR_VSA_PowerOn_017,		
33	START_TIME,VSA_OPNAV_017-03:12:00,		
34	TITLE, "VIR Power on",		
35	REQUESTOR, "sfonte",		
36	PROCESSOR, "GSC1",		
37	KEY, "No_Key")		
38			
39	spawn(1,		
40	SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,		
41	REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,		
42	RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on,"VIR_P","SAFE")		
43),		
44	note(1,		
45	SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:07:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,		
46	TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_PowerOn_017: Power on VML sequence is finished;"\		
47),		
48	end;		
49			
50	request(VIR_VSA_CryocoolerOn_017,		
51	START_TIME,VSA_OPNAV_017-03:02:00,		
52	TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",		
53	REQUESTOR, "sfonte",		
54	PROCESSOR, "GSC1",		
55	KEY, "No_Key")		
56			
57	command(1,		
58	SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,		
59	NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CryocoolerOn_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\<,		
60	VIR_TC_STAND_BY()		
61),		
62	command(2,		
63	SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,		
64	NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CryocoolerOn_017: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN."\<,		
65	VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",75,0)		
66),		
67	note(1,		
68	SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:59:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,		
69	TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CryocoolerOn_017: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour waiting."\<		
70),		
71	end;		
72			
73	request(VIR_VSA_OpenCover_017,		
74	START_TIME,VSA_OPNAV_017-00:02:00,		
75	TITLE, "VIR open cover",		
76	REQUESTOR, "sfonte",		
77	PROCESSOR, "GSC1",		
78	KEY, "No_Key")		
79			
80	command(1,		
81	SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,		
82	NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_OpenCover_017: Set for opening the cover."\<,		
83	VIR_TC_COVER("OPENCOVER")		

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84     ),
85     note(1,
86         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
87         TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_OpenCover_017: Cover is open." \
88     ),
89     end;
90
91     request(VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017,
92         START_TIME,VSA_OPNAV_017+00:00:01,
93         TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, directly Virtual Recorder storing.",
94         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
95         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
96         KEY, "No_Key")
97
98     command(1,
99         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
100        NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: SP_MODE_5_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_5_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_5_STEP_ALFA to
        perform 4 scan mirror steps" \,
101        VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,23,24,25,72000,90000,4500)
102    ),
103    command(2,
104        SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
105        NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
        RepTime,Integration time IR=1.0s VIS=10.0s" \,
106
107        VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,50,230,500,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"VIR_TM
108    ),
109    command(3,
110        SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
111        COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556" \,
112        NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \,
113        VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
114    ),
115    command(4,
116        SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
117        NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
118        VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
119    ),
120    note(1,
121        SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
122        TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Cube N.1 Data Volume in VR 0.010 Gibit" \
123    ),
124    command(5,
125        SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
126        NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
        RepTime,Integration time IR=1.8s VIS=10.0s" \,
127
128        VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,90,210,500,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"VIR_TM
129    ),
130    command(6,
131        SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
132        COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556" \,
133        NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \,
134        VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
135    ),
136    command(7,
137        SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
138        NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,

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137     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
138   ),
139   note(2,
140     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
141     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Cube N.2 Data Volume in VR 0.020 Gibit"\
142   ),
143   command(8,
144     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
145     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
146       RepTime,Integration time IR=2.5s VIS=10.0s"\,
147     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,125,192,500,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"VIR_T
148   ),
149   command(9,
150     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
151     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
152     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
153     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
154   ),
155   command(10,
156     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
157     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
158     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
159   ),
160   note(3,
161     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
162     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Cube N.3 Data Volume in VR 0.029 Gibit"\
163   ),
164   command(11,
165     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
166     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
167       RepTime,Integration time IR=4.0s VIS=10.0s"\,
168     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,200,155,500,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"VIR_T
169   ),
170   command(12,
171     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
172     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
173     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
174     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
175   ),
176   command(13,
177     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
178     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
179     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
180   ),
181   note(4,
182     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
183     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Cube N.4 Data Volume in VR 0.039 Gibit"\
184   ),
185   command(14,
186     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
187     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
188       RepTime,Integration time IR=1.0s VIS=9.0s"\,
189     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,50,205,450,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"VIR_TM
190   ),
191   command(15,

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189     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
190     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
191     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
192     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
193   ),
194   command(16,
195     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
196     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
197     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
198   ),
199   note(5,
200     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
201     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Cube N.5 Data Volume in VR 0.049 Gibit"\
202   ),
203   command(17,
204     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
205     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
RepTime,Integration time IR=1.8s VIS=9.0s"\,
206     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,90,185,450,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"VIR_TM
207   ),
208   command(18,
209     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
210     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
211     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
212     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
213   ),
214   command(19,
215     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
216     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
217     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
218   ),
219   note(6,
220     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
221     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Cube N.6 Data Volume in VR 0.059 Gibit"\
222   ),
223   command(20,
224     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
225     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
RepTime,Integration time IR=2.5s VIS=9.0s"\,
226     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,125,167,450,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"VIR_T
227   ),
228   command(21,
229     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
230     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
231     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
232     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
233   ),
234   command(22,
235     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
236     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
237     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
238   ),
239   note(7,
240     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
241     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Cube N.7 Data Volume in VR 0.068 Gibit"\
242   ),

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243     command(23,
244         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
245         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
                RepTime,Integration time IR=4.0s VIS=9.0s"\,
246         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,200,130,450,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"VIR_T
247     ),
248     command(24,
249         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
250         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
251         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
252         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
253     ),
254     command(25,
255         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
256         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
257         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
258     ),
259     note(8,
260         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
261         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Cube N.8 Data Volume in VR 0.078 Gibit"\
262     ),
263     command(26,
264         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
265         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
                RepTime,Integration time IR=1.0s VIS=8.0s"\,
266         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,50,180,400,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"VIR_TM
267     ),
268     command(27,
269         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
270         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
271         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
272         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
273     ),
274     command(28,
275         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
276         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
277         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
278     ),
279     note(9,
280         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
281         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Cube N.9 Data Volume in VR 0.088 Gibit"\
282     ),
283     command(29,
284         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
285         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
                RepTime,Integration time IR=1.8s VIS=8.0s"\,
286         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,90,160,400,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"VIR_TM
287     ),
288     command(30,
289         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
290         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
291         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
292         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
293     ),
294     command(31,

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295     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
296     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
297     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
298   ),
299   note(10,
300     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
301     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Cube N.10 Data Volume in VR 0.098 Gibit"\\
302   ),
303   command(32,
304     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
305     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
      RepTime,Integration time IR=2.5s VIS=8.0s"\\,
306     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,125,142,400,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"VIR_T
307   ),
308   command(33,
309     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
310     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\\,
311     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,
312     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
313   ),
314   command(34,
315     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
316     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
317     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
318   ),
319   note(11,
320     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
321     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Cube N.11 Data Volume in VR 0.107 Gibit"\\
322   ),
323   command(35,
324     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
325     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
      RepTime,Integration time IR=4.0s VIS=8.0s"\\,
326     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,200,105,400,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"VIR_T
327   ),
328   command(36,
329     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
330     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\\,
331     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,
332     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
333   ),
334   command(37,
335     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
336     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
337     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
338   ),
339   note(12,
340     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
341     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Cube N.12 Data Volume in VR 0.117 Gibit"\\
342   ),
343   command(38,
344     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
345     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
      RepTime,Integration time IR=1.0s VIS=12.5s"\\,
346     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,50,292,625,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"VIR_TM

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347     ),
348     command(39,
349         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
350         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
351         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
352         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
353     ),
354     command(40,
355         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
356         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
357         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
358     ),
359     note(13,
360         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
361         TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Cube N.13 Data Volume in VR 0.135 Gibit"\
362     ),
363     command(41,
364         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
365         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
366         RepTime,Integration time IR=1.8s VIS=12.5s"\,
367         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,90,272,625,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"VIR_TM
368     ),
369     command(42,
370         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
371         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
372         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
373         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
374     ),
375     command(43,
376         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
377         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
378         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
379     ),
380     note(14,
381         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
382         TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Cube N.14 Data Volume in VR 0.152 Gibit"\
383     ),
384     command(44,
385         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
386         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
387         RepTime,Integration time IR=2.5s VIS=12.5s"\,
388         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,125,255,625,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"VIR_T
389     ),
390     command(45,
391         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
392         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
393         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
394         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
395     ),
396     command(46,
397         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
398         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
399         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
400     ),
401     note(15,
402         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,

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401     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Cube N.15 Data Volume in VR 0.170 Gibit"\
402   ),
403   command(47,
404     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
405     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
      RepTime,Integration time IR=4.0s VIS=12.5s"\,
406     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,200,217,625,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"VIR_T
407   ),
408   command(48,
409     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
410     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
411     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
412     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
413   ),
414   command(49,
415     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
416     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
417     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
418   ),
419   note(16,
420     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
421     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Cube N.16 Data Volume in VR 0.187 Gibit"\
422   ),
423   command(50,
424     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
425     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
      RepTime,Integration time IR=1.0s VIS=11.0s"\,
426     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,50,255,550,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"VIR_TM
427   ),
428   command(51,
429     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
430     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
431     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
432     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
433   ),
434   command(52,
435     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
436     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
437     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
438   ),
439   note(17,
440     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
441     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Cube N.17 Data Volume in VR 0.205 Gibit"\
442   ),
443   command(53,
444     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
445     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
      RepTime,Integration time IR=1.8s VIS=11.0s"\,
446     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,90,235,550,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"VIR_TM
447   ),
448   command(54,
449     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
450     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
451     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
452     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")

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453     ),
454     command(55,
455         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
456         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
457         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
458     ),
459     note(18,
460         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
461         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Cube N.18 Data Volume in VR 0.222 Gibit"\\
462     ),
463     command(56,
464         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
465         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
         RepTime,Integration time IR=2.5s VIS=11.0s"\\,
466         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,125,217,550,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"VIR_T
467     ),
468     command(57,
469         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
470         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\\,
471         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,
472         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
473     ),
474     command(58,
475         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
476         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
477         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
478     ),
479     note(19,
480         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
481         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Cube N.19 Data Volume in VR 0.240 Gibit"\\
482     ),
483     command(59,
484         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
485         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
         RepTime,Integration time IR=4.0s VIS=11.0s"\\,
486         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,200,180,550,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"VIR_T
487     ),
488     command(60,
489         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
490         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\\,
491         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,
492         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
493     ),
494     command(61,
495         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
496         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
497         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
498     ),
499     note(20,
500         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
501         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Cube N.20 Data Volume in VR 0.257 Gibit"\\
502     ),
503     command(62,
504         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
505         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
         RepTime,Integration time IR=1.0s VIS=10.0s"\\,

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506     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,50,230,500,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"VIR_TM
507   ),
508   command(63,
509     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
510     COMMENT,"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
511     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
512     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
513   ),
514   command(64,
515     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
516     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
517     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
518   ),
519   note(21,
520     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
521     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Cube N.21 Data Volume in VR 0.275 Gibit"\
522   ),
523   command(65,
524     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
525     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
      RepTime,Integration time IR=1.8s VIS=10.0s"\,
526
527     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,90,210,500,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"VIR_TM
528   ),
529   command(66,
530     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
531     COMMENT,"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
532     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
533     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
534   ),
535   command(67,
536     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
537     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
538     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
539   ),
540   note(22,
541     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
542     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Cube N.22 Data Volume in VR 0.293 Gibit"\
543   ),
544   command(68,
545     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
546     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
      RepTime,Integration time IR=2.5s VIS=10.0s"\,
547
548     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,125,192,500,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"VIR_T
549   ),
550   command(69,
551     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
552     COMMENT,"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
553     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
554     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
555   ),
556   command(70,
557     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
558     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
559     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
560   ),

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559     note(23,
560         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
561         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Cube N.23 Data Volume in VR 0.310 Gibit"\
562     ),
563     command(71,
564         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
565         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
          RepTime,Integration time IR=4.0s VIS=10.0s"\,
566         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,200,155,500,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"VIR_T
567     ),
568     command(72,
569         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
570         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
571         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
572         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
573     ),
574     command(73,
575         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
576         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
577         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
578     ),
579     note(24,
580         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
581         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Cube N.24 Data Volume in VR 0.328 Gibit"\
582     ),
583     command(74,
584         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
585         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
          RepTime,Integration time IR=1.0s VIS=9.0s"\,
586         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,50,205,450,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"VIR_TM
587     ),
588     command(75,
589         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
590         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
591         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
592         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
593     ),
594     command(76,
595         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
596         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
597         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
598     ),
599     note(25,
600         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
601         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Cube N.25 Data Volume in VR 0.345 Gibit"\
602     ),
603     command(77,
604         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
605         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
          RepTime,Integration time IR=1.8s VIS=9.0s"\,
606         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,90,185,450,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"VIR_TM
607     ),
608     command(78,
609         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
610         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,

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611     NTEXT, \ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \ ,
612     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
613   ),
614   command(79,
615     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:02:05 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
616     NTEXT, \ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \ ,
617     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
618   ),
619   note(26,
620     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:00:05 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
621     TEXT, \ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Cube N.26 Data Volume in VR 0.363 Gibit" \
622   ),
623   command(80,
624     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:00:01 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
625     NTEXT, \ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
        RepTime,Integration time IR=2.5s VIS=9.0s" \ ,
626     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F", 15,5,125,167,450,5,5, "IR_VIS", "ALL_SUBFRAMES", "ON", 5, "VIR_T
627   ),
628   command(81,
629     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:00:05 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
630     COMMENT, \ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556" \ ,
631     NTEXT, \ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \ ,
632     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
633   ),
634   command(82,
635     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:02:05 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
636     NTEXT, \ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \ ,
637     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
638   ),
639   note(27,
640     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:00:05 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
641     TEXT, \ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Cube N.27 Data Volume in VR 0.380 Gibit" \
642   ),
643   command(83,
644     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:00:01 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
645     NTEXT, \ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
        RepTime,Integration time IR=4.0s VIS=9.0s" \ ,
646     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F", 15,5,200,130,450,5,5, "IR_VIS", "ALL_SUBFRAMES", "ON", 5, "VIR_T
647   ),
648   command(84,
649     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:00:05 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
650     COMMENT, \ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556" \ ,
651     NTEXT, \ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \ ,
652     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
653   ),
654   command(85,
655     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:02:05 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
656     NTEXT, \ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \ ,
657     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
658   ),
659   note(28,
660     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:00:05 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
661     TEXT, \ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Cube N.28 Data Volume in VR 0.398 Gibit" \
662   ),
663   command(86,
664     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:00:01 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,

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665 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
RepTime,Integration time IR=1.0s VIS=8.0s"\,
666 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,50,180,400,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"VIR_TM
667 ),
668 command(87,
669 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
670 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
671 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
672 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
673 ),
674 command(88,
675 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
676 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
677 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
678 ),
679 note(29,
680 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
681 TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Cube N.29 Data Volume in VR 0.415 Gibit"\
682 ),
683 command(89,
684 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
685 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
RepTime,Integration time IR=1.8s VIS=8.0s"\,
686 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,90,160,400,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"VIR_TM
687 ),
688 command(90,
689 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
690 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
691 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
692 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
693 ),
694 command(91,
695 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
696 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
697 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
698 ),
699 note(30,
700 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
701 TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Cube N.30 Data Volume in VR 0.433 Gibit"\
702 ),
703 command(92,
704 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
705 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
RepTime,Integration time IR=2.5s VIS=8.0s"\,
706 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,125,142,400,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"VIR_T
707 ),
708 command(93,
709 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
710 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
711 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
712 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
713 ),
714 command(94,
715 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
716 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",

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717     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
718     ),
719     note(31,
720         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
721         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Cube N.31 Data Volume in VR 0.451 Gibit"\
722     ),
723     command(95,
724         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
725         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
726             RepTime,Integration time IR=4.0s VIS=8.0s"\,
727         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,200,105,400,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"VIR_T
728     ),
729     command(96,
730         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
731         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
732         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
733         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
734     ),
735     command(97,
736         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
737         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
738         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
739     ),
740     note(32,
741         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
742         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_017: Cube N.32 Data Volume in VR 0.468 Gibit"\
743     ),
744     end;
745     request(VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017,
746         START_TIME,VSA_OPNAV_017+01:13:01,
747         TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
748         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
749         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
750         KEY, "No_Key")
751
752     command(1,
753         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
754         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: SP_MODE_5_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_5_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_5_STEP_ALFA to
755             perform 4 scan mirror steps"\,
756         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,23,24,25,72000,90000,4500)
757     ),
758     command(2,
759         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
760         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
761             RepTime,Integration time IR=1.0s VIS=12.5s"\,
762         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,50,292,625,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"NO_VIR
763     ),
764     command(3,
765         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
766         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
767         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
768         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
769     ),
770     command(4,
771         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,

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770     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
771     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
772   ),
773   note(1,
774     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
775     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.017 Gibit" \
776   ),
777   command(5,
778     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
779     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
      RepTime,Integration time IR=1.8s VIS=12.5s" \,
780     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,90,272,625,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"NO_VI
781   ),
782   command(6,
783     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
784     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556" \,
785     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \,
786     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
787   ),
788   command(7,
789     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
790     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
791     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
792   ),
793   note(2,
794     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
795     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.035 Gibit" \
796   ),
797   command(8,
798     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
799     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
      RepTime,Integration time IR=2.5s VIS=12.5s" \,
800     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,125,255,625,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"NO_VI
801   ),
802   command(9,
803     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
804     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556" \,
805     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \,
806     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
807   ),
808   command(10,
809     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
810     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
811     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
812   ),
813   note(3,
814     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
815     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.052 Gibit" \
816   ),
817   command(11,
818     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
819     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
      RepTime,Integration time IR=4.0s VIS=12.5s" \,
820     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,200,217,625,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"NO_VI
821   ),

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822     command(12,
823         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
824         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
825         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
826         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
827     ),
828     command(13,
829         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
830         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
831         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
832     ),
833     note(4,
834         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
835         TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.070 Gibit"\
836     ),
837     command(14,
838         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
839         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
            RepTime,Integration time IR=1.0s VIS=11.0s"\,
840         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,50,255,550,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"NO_VIR
841     ),
842     command(15,
843         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
844         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
845         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
846         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
847     ),
848     command(16,
849         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
850         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
851         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
852     ),
853     note(5,
854         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
855         TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.087 Gibit"\
856     ),
857     command(17,
858         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
859         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
            RepTime,Integration time IR=1.8s VIS=11.0s"\,
860         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,90,235,550,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"NO_VIR
861     ),
862     command(18,
863         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
864         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
865         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
866         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
867     ),
868     command(19,
869         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
870         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
871         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
872     ),
873     note(6,
874         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
875         TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Cube N.6 Data Volume in MM 0.104 Gibit"\

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876     ),
877     command(20,
878         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
879         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
            RepTime,Integration time IR=2.5s VIS=11.0s"\,
880         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,125,217,550,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"NO_VI
881     ),
882     command(21,
883         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
884         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
885         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
886         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
887     ),
888     command(22,
889         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
890         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
891         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
892     ),
893     note(7,
894         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
895         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Cube N.7 Data Volume in MM 0.122 Gibit"\
896     ),
897     command(23,
898         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
899         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
            RepTime,Integration time IR=4.0s VIS=11.0s"\,
900         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,200,180,550,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"NO_VI
901     ),
902     command(24,
903         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
904         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
905         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
906         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
907     ),
908     command(25,
909         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
910         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
911         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
912     ),
913     note(8,
914         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
915         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Cube N.8 Data Volume in MM 0.139 Gibit"\
916     ),
917     command(26,
918         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
919         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
            RepTime,Integration time IR=1.0s VIS=10.0s"\,
920         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,50,230,500,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"NO_VIR
921     ),
922     command(27,
923         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
924         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
925         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
926         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
927     ),

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928     command(28,
929         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
930         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
931         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
932     ),
933     note(9,
934         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
935         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Cube N.9 Data Volume in MM 0.157 Gibit"\\
936     ),
937     command(29,
938         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
939         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
          RepTime,Integration time IR=1.8s VIS=10.0s"\\,
940         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,90,210,500,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"NO_VIR
941     ),
942     command(30,
943         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
944         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\\,
945         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,
946         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
947     ),
948     command(31,
949         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
950         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
951         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
952     ),
953     note(10,
954         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
955         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Cube N.10 Data Volume in MM 0.174 Gibit"\\
956     ),
957     command(32,
958         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
959         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
          RepTime,Integration time IR=2.5s VIS=10.0s"\\,
960         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,125,192,500,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"NO_VI
961     ),
962     command(33,
963         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
964         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\\,
965         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,
966         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
967     ),
968     command(34,
969         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
970         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
971         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
972     ),
973     note(11,
974         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
975         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Cube N.11 Data Volume in MM 0.191 Gibit"\\
976     ),
977     command(35,
978         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
979         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
          RepTime,Integration time IR=4.0s VIS=10.0s"\\,

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980     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,200,155,500,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"NO_VI
981     ),
982     command(36,
983     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
984     COMMENT,"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
985     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
986     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
987     ),
988     command(37,
989     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
990     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
991     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
992     ),
993     note(12,
994     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
995     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Cube N.12 Data Volume in MM 0.209 Gibit"\
996     ),
997     command(38,
998     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
999     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
    RepTime,Integration time IR=1.0s VIS=9.0s"\,
1000
1001     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,50,205,450,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"NO_VIR
1002     ),
1003     command(39,
1004     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1005     COMMENT,"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
1006     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1007     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1008     ),
1009     command(40,
1010     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1011     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
1012     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1013     ),
1014     note(13,
1015     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1016     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Cube N.13 Data Volume in MM 0.226 Gibit"\
1017     ),
1018     command(41,
1019     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1020     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
    RepTime,Integration time IR=1.8s VIS=9.0s"\,
1021
1022     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,90,185,450,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"NO_VIR
1023     ),
1024     command(42,
1025     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1026     COMMENT,"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
1027     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1028     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1029     ),
1030     command(43,
1031     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1032     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
1033     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1034     ),

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1033     note(14,
1034         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1035         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Cube N.14 Data Volume in MM 0.244 Gibit"\
1036     ),
1037     command(44,
1038         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1039         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
1040             RepTime,Integration time IR=2.5s VIS=9.0s"\,
1041         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,125,167,450,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"NO_VI
1042     ),
1043     command(45,
1044         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1045         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
1046         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1047         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1048     ),
1049     command(46,
1050         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1051         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
1052         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1053     ),
1054     note(15,
1055         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1056         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Cube N.15 Data Volume in MM 0.261 Gibit"\
1057     ),
1058     command(47,
1059         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1060         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
1061             RepTime,Integration time IR=4.0s VIS=9.0s"\,
1062         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,200,130,450,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"NO_VI
1063     ),
1064     command(48,
1065         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1066         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
1067         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1068         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1069     ),
1070     command(49,
1071         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1072         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
1073         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1074     ),
1075     note(16,
1076         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1077         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Cube N.16 Data Volume in MM 0.278 Gibit"\
1078     ),
1079     command(50,
1080         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1081         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
1082             RepTime,Integration time IR=1.0s VIS=8.0s"\,
1083         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,50,180,400,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"NO_VIR
1084     ),
1085     command(51,
1086         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1087         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,

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1085     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1086     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1087   ),
1088   command(52,
1089     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1090     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
1091     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1092   ),
1093   note(17,
1094     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1095     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Cube N.17 Data Volume in MM 0.296 Gibit"\
1096   ),
1097   command(53,
1098     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1099     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
1100     RepTime,Integration time IR=1.8s VIS=8.0s"\,
1101     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,90,160,400,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"NO_VIR
1102   ),
1103   command(54,
1104     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1105     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
1106     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1107     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1108   ),
1109   command(55,
1110     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1111     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
1112     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1113   ),
1114   note(18,
1115     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1116     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Cube N.18 Data Volume in MM 0.313 Gibit"\
1117   ),
1118   command(56,
1119     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1120     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
1121     RepTime,Integration time IR=2.5s VIS=8.0s"\,
1122     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,125,142,400,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"NO_VI
1123   ),
1124   command(57,
1125     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1126     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
1127     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1128     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1129   ),
1130   command(58,
1131     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1132     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
1133     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1134   ),
1135   note(19,
1136     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1137     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Cube N.19 Data Volume in MM 0.331 Gibit"\
1138   ),
1139   command(59,
1140     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,

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1139 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,5 frame,15
RepTime,Integration time IR=4.0s VIS=8.0s"\,
1140 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,5,200,105,400,5,5,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"NO_VI
1141 ),
1142 command(60,
1143 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1144 COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
1145 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1146 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1147 ),
1148 command(61,
1149 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1150 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
1151 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1152 ),
1153 note(20,
1154 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1155 TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_017: Cube N.20 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit"\
1156 ),
1157 end;
1158
1159 request(VIR_VSA_CloseCover_017,
1160 START_TIME,VSA_OPNAV_017+01:58:26,
1161 TITLE, "VIR close cover",
1162 REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1163 PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1164 KEY, "No_Key")
1165
1166 command(1,
1167 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1168 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CloseCover_017: Set for closing the cover.""\,
1169 VIR_TC_COVER("CLOSECOVER")
1170 ),
1171 note(1,
1172 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1173 TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CloseCover_017: Cover is closed.""\
1174 ),
1175 end;
1176
1177 request(VIR_VSA_CryocoolerOff_017,
1178 START_TIME,VSA_OPNAV_017+01:59:26,
1179 TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",
1180 REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1181 PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1182 KEY, "No_Key")
1183
1184 command(1,
1185 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1186 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CryocoolerOff_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
1187 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1188 ),
1189 command(2,
1190 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1191 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CryocoolerOff_017: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime.""\,
1192 VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)
1193 ),
1194 note(1,

```

```

1195     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1196     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CryocoolerOff_017: the cryocooling is off.\"\\
1197   ),
1198 end;
1199
1200 request(VIR_VSA_DumpDataToVR4_017,
1201     START_TIME,VSA_OPNAV_017+08:34:00,
1202     TITLE, \"VIR dump data into VR4\",
1203     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
1204     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
1205     KEY, \"No_Key\")
1206
1207     command(1,
1208     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1209     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_DumpDataToVR4_017: begin data dumping into VR4.\"\\,
1210     VIR_MM_DUMP(\"LOSSLESS\")
1211   ),
1212     command(2,
1213     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:29:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1214     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_DumpDataToVR4_017: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1215     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1216   ),
1217     note(1,
1218     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1219     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_DumpDataToVR4_017: data volume in VR4 0.195 Gibit.\"\\
1220   ),
1221 end;
1222
1223 request(VIR_VSA_PowerOff_017,
1224     START_TIME,VSA_OPNAV_017+09:06:00,
1225     TITLE, \"VIR Power off\",
1226     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
1227     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
1228     KEY, \"No_Key\")
1229
1230     note(1,
1231     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1232     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_PowerOff_017: Power off VIR instrument.\"\\
1233   ),
1234     spawn(1,
1235     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1236     REQ_ENGINE_ID,\\"ANY_ENGINE\",
1237     RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)
1238   ),
1239 end;
1240
1241 $$EOF

```

The following SASF files were processed:

7.2 The sequence: vir_vsa_OpNav_018.r07.sasf

```

1  CCSD3ZF0000100000001NJPL3KS0L015$$MARK$$;
2  MISSION_NAME = DAWN;
3  SPACECRAFT_NAME = DAWN;
4  DATA_SET_ID = SPACECRAFT_ACTIVITY_SEQUENCE_DSC;
5  FILE_NAME = vir_vsa_OpNav_018.r07.sasf;
6  APPLICABLE_START_TIME = 2011-197T05:00:00.000;

```

```

7  APPLICABLE_STOP_TIME = 2011-212T05:00:00.000;
8  PRODUCT_CREATION_TIME = 2011-165T14:35:16.000;
9  PRODUCER_ID = VIRTEAM;
10 SEQ_ID = vir_vsa_OpNav_018.r07;
11 HOST_ID = dawndsc2;
12 CCSD3RE00000$$MARK$$NJPL3IF0M01300000001;
13 $$DWN      SPACECRAFT ACTIVITY SEQUENCE FILE
14 *****
15 *PROJECT    DWN
16 *SPACECRAFT 203
17 *OPERATOR   sfonte
18 *FILE_CMPLT TRUE
19 *DATE       Tue Jun 14 14:35:16 2011
20 *SEQGEN     V29.5.2 Thu Nov 29 13:34:23 PST 2007
21 *BEGIN      2011-197T05:00:00.000
22 *CUTOFF     2011-212T05:00:00.000
23 *TITLE      VIR_VSA_OPNAV_018_da004
24 *EPOCHS_DEF
25 *VSA_OPNAV_018, 2011-199T20:36:00.000
26 *EPOCHS_END
27 *Input files used:
28 *File Type  Last modified          File name
29 *****
30 $$EOH
31 $$EOD
32 request(VIR_VSA_PowerOn_018,
33         START_TIME,VSA_OPNAV_018-04:00:00,
34         TITLE, "VIR Power on",
35         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
36         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
37         KEY, "No_Key")
38
39 spawn(1,
40       SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
41       REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
42       RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on,"VIR_P","SAFE")
43     ),
44     note(1,
45         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:07:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
46         TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_PowerOn_018: Power on VML sequence is finished;"\
47     ),
48 end;
49
50 request(VIR_VSA_FullCalibration_018,
51         START_TIME,VSA_OPNAV_018-03:50:00,
52         TITLE, "VIR cooldown and full calibration sequence",
53         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
54         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
55         KEY, "No_Key")
56
57 spawn(1,
58       SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
59       REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
60       RT_on_board_block(vcfl_vir_calibration_full)
61     ),
62     command(1,
63         SCHEDULED_TIME,\03:30:10\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,

```

```

64     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_FullCalibration_018: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY"\,
65     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
66   ),
67   note(1,
68     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
69     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_FullCalibration_018: Full Calibration VML is finished."\
70   ),
71   note(2,
72     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
73     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_FullCalibration_018: Data Volume in VR4: 0.126 Gibit,120 pages, 15960 packets."\
74   ),
75 end;
76
77 request(VIR_VSA_OpenCover_018,
78   START_TIME,VSA_OPNAV_018-00:02:00,
79   TITLE, "VIR open cover",
80   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
81   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
82   KEY, "No_Key")
83
84   command(1,
85     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
86     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_OpenCover_018: Set for opening the cover."\,
87     VIR_TC_COVER("OPENCOVER")
88   ),
89   note(1,
90     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
91     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_OpenCover_018: Cover is open."\
92   ),
93 end;
94
95 request(VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_018a,
96   START_TIME,VSA_OPNAV_018+00:00:30,
97   TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
98   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
99   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
100  KEY, "No_Key")
101
102  command(1,
103    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
104    NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_018a: SP_MODE_5_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_5_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_5_STEP_ALFA to
105    perform 196 scan mirror steps"\,
106    VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,23,24,25,-441000,436500,4500)
107  ),
108  command(2,
109    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
110    NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_018a: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,201
111    frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=1.8s VIS=12.0s"\,
112    VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,50,90,260,600,5,201,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"NO_V
113  ),
114  command(3,
115    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
116    COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
117    NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_018a: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
118    VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
119  ),
120  command(4,

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119     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:50:51\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
120     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_018a: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
121     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
122   ),
123   note(1,
124     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
125     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_018a: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.699 Gibit"\\
126   ),
127 end;
128
129 request(VIR_VSA_DumpDataToVR4_018a,
130   START_TIME,VSA_OPNAV_018+00:51:40,
131   TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
132   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
133   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
134   KEY, "No_Key")
135
136   command(1,
137     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
138     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_DumpDataToVR4_018a: begin data dumping into VR4."\\,
139     VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
140   ),
141   command(2,
142     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
143     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_DumpDataToVR4_018a: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
144     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
145   ),
146   note(1,
147     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
148     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_DumpDataToVR4_018a: data volume in VR4 0.116 Gibit."\\
149   ),
150 end;
151
152 request(VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_018b,
153   START_TIME,VSA_OPNAV_018+01:05:40,
154   TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
155   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
156   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
157   KEY, "No_Key")
158
159   command(1,
160     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
161     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_018b: SP_MODE_5_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_5_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_5_STEP_ALFA to
162     perform 196 scan mirror steps"\\,
163     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,23,24,25,-441000,436500,4500)
164   ),
165   command(2,
166     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
167     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_018b: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,201
168     frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.5s VIS=12.0s"\\,
169     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,50,125,242,600,5,201,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"NO
170   ),
171   command(3,
172     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
173     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\\,
174     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_018b: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,
175     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")

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174     ),
175     command(4,
176         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:50:51\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
177         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_018b: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
178         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
179     ),
180     note(1,
181         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
182         TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_018b: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 1.191 Gibit" \
183     ),
184 end;
185
186 request(VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_018c,
187     START_TIME,VSA_OPNAV_018+01:56:46,
188     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
189     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
190     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
191     KEY, "No_Key")
192
193     command(1,
194         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
195         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_018c: SP_MODE_5_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_5_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_5_STEP_ALFA to
196         perform 98 scan mirror steps" \,
197         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,23,24,25,-220500,216000,4500)
198     ),
199     command(2,
200         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
201         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_018c: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,101 frame,7
202         RepTime,Integratation time IR=4.0s VIS=0.0s" \,
203         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",7,50,200,5,0,105,101,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"NO_VI
204     ),
205     command(3,
206         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
207         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556" \,
208         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_018c: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \,
209         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
210     ),
211     command(4,
212         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:12:23\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
213         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_018c: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
214         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
215     ),
216     note(1,
217         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
218         TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_018c: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 1.367 Gibit" \
219     ),
220 end;
221
222 request(VIR_VSA_CloseCover_018,
223     START_TIME,VSA_OPNAV_018+02:11:01,
224     TITLE, "VIR cclose cover",
225     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
226     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
227     KEY, "No_Key")
228
229     command(1,
230         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,

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229     NTEXT, \"VIR_VSA_CloseCover_018: Set for closing the cover.\" \,
230     VIR_TC_COVER(\"CLOSECOVER\")
231   ),
232   note(1,
233     SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:01:00 \, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
234     TEXT, \"VIR_VSA_CloseCover_018: Cover is closed.\" \
235   ),
236 end;
237
238 request(VIR_VSA_CryocoolerOff_018,
239   START_TIME, VSA_OPNAV_018+02:12:01,
240   TITLE, \"VIR cryocooler off\",
241   REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
242   PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
243   KEY, \"No_Key\")
244
245   command(1,
246     SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:00:00 \, FROM_REQUEST_START,
247     NTEXT, \"VIR_VSA_CryocoolerOff_018: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\" \,
248     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
249   ),
250   command(2,
251     SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:00:05 \, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
252     NTEXT, \"VIR_VSA_CryocoolerOff_018: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime.\" \,
253     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN(\"OFF\", 75, 2500)
254   ),
255   note(1,
256     SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:00:01 \, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
257     TEXT, \"VIR_VSA_CryocoolerOff_018: the cryocooling is off.\" \
258   ),
259 end;
260
261 request(VIR_VSA_DumpDataToVR4_018b,
262   START_TIME, VSA_OPNAV_018+07:08:00,
263   TITLE, \"VIR dump data into VR4\",
264   REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
265   PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
266   KEY, \"No_Key\")
267
268   command(1,
269     SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:00:00 \, FROM_REQUEST_START,
270     NTEXT, \"VIR_VSA_DumpDataToVR4_018b: begin data dumping into VR4.\" \,
271     VIR_MM_DUMP(\"LOSSLESS\")
272   ),
273   command(2,
274     SCHEDULED_TIME, \01:49:55 \, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
275     NTEXT, \"VIR_VSA_DumpDataToVR4_018b: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\" \,
276     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
277   ),
278   note(1,
279     SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:00:05 \, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
280     TEXT, \"VIR_VSA_DumpDataToVR4_018b: data volume in VR4 1.029 Gibit.\" \
281   ),
282 end;
283
284 request(VIR_VSA_PowerOff_018,
285   START_TIME, VSA_OPNAV_018+08:58:00,
```

```

286     TITLE, "VIR Power off",
287     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
288     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
289     KEY, "No_Key")
290
291     note(1,
292         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
293         TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_PowerOff_018: Power off VIR instrument." \
294     ),
295     spawn(1,
296         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
297         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
298         RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)
299     ),
300 end;
301
302 $$EOF
  
```

The following SASF files were processed:

7.3 The sequence: vir_vsa_OpNav_019.r06.sasf

```

1  CCSD3ZF0000100000001NJPL3KS0L015$$MARK$$;
2  MISSION_NAME = DAWN;
3  SPACECRAFT_NAME = DAWN;
4  DATA_SET_ID = SPACECRAFT_ACTIVITY_SEQUENCE_DSC;
5  FILE_NAME = vir_vsa_OpNav_019.r06.sasf;
6  APPLICABLE_START_TIME = 2011-197T05:00:00.000;
7  APPLICABLE_STOP_TIME = 2011-212T05:00:00.000;
8  PRODUCT_CREATION_TIME = 2011-187T08:17:15.000;
9  PRODUCER_ID = VIRTEAM;
10 SEQ_ID = vir_vsa_OpNav_019.r06;
11 HOST_ID = dawndsc2;
12 CCSD3RE00000$$MARK$$NJPL3IF0M01300000001;
13 $$DWN     SPACECRAFT ACTIVITY SEQUENCE FILE
14 *****
15 *PROJECT   DWN
16 *SPACECRAFT 203
17 *OPERATOR  sfonte
18 *FILE_CMPLT TRUE
19 *DATE      Wed Jul 06 08:17:15 2011
20 *SEQGEN    V29.5.2 Thu Nov 29 13:34:23 PST 2007
21 *BEGIN     2011-197T05:00:00.000
22 *CUTOFF    2011-212T05:00:00.000
23 *TITLE     VIR_VSA_OPNAV_019_da004
24 *EPOCHS_DEF
25 *VSA_OPNAV_019, 2011-204T19:15:00.000
26 *EPOCHS_END
27 *Input files used:
28 *File Type Last modified      File name
29 *****
30 $$EOH
31 $$EOD
32 request(VIR_VSA_PowerOn_019,
33     START_TIME,VSA_OPNAV_019-03:47:00,
34     TITLE, "VIR Power on",
35     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
36     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
  
```

```
37     KEY, "No_Key")
38
39     spawn(1,
40         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
41         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
42         RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on,"VIR_P","SAFE")
43     ),
44     note(1,
45         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:07:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
46         TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_PowerOn_019: Power on VML sequence is finished;"\
47     ),
48 end;
49
50 request(VIR_VSA_FullCalibration_019,
51     START_TIME,VSA_OPNAV_019-03:37:00,
52     TITLE, "VIR cooldown and full calibration sequence",
53     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
54     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
55     KEY, "No_Key")
56
57     spawn(1,
58         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
59         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
60         RT_on_board_block(vcfl_vir_calibration_full)
61     ),
62     command(1,
63         SCHEDULED_TIME,\03:30:10\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
64         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_FullCalibration_019: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY"\,
65         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
66     ),
67     note(1,
68         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
69         TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_FullCalibration_019: Full Calibration VML is finished."\<
70     ),
71     note(2,
72         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
73         TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_FullCalibration_019: Data Volume in VR4: 0.126 Gbit,120 pages, 15960 packets."\<
74     ),
75 end;
76
77 request(VIR_VSA_OpenCover_019,
78     START_TIME,VSA_OPNAV_019-00:02:00,
79     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
80     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
81     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
82     KEY, "No_Key")
83
84     command(1,
85         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
86         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_OpenCover_019: Set for opening the cover."\<,
87         VIR_TC_COVER("OPENCOVER")
88     ),
89     note(1,
90         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
91         TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_OpenCover_019: Cover is open."\<
92     ),
93 end;
```

```

94
95 request(VIR_VSA_CubeToMM2VR4_019,
96     START_TIME,VSA_OPNAV_019+00:00:30,
97     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, directly Virtual Recorder storing.",
98     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
99     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
100    KEY, "No_Key")
101
102    command(1,
103        SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
104        NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToMM2VR4_019: SP_MODE_6_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_6_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_6_STEP_ALFA
to perform 64 scan mirror steps"\,
105        VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,26,27,28,-576000,-292500,4500)
106    ),
107    command(2,
108        SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
109        NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToMM2VR4_019: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,66
frame,16 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.7s VIS=13.0s"\,
110        VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",16,65,35,312,650,5,66,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",6,"NO_VI
111    ),
112    command(3,
113        SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
114        COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
115        NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToMM2VR4_019: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
116        VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
117    ),
118    command(4,
119        SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:18:12\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
120        NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToMM2VR4_019: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
121        VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
122    ),
123    note(1,
124        SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
125        TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToMM2VR4_019: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.230 Gibit"\
126    ),
127    command(5,
128        SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
129        NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToMM2VR4_019: begin data dumping into VR4.""\,
130        VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
131    ),
132    command(6,
133        SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:08:40\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
134        NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToMM2VR4_019: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
135        VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
136    ),
137    note(2,
138        SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
139        TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToMM2VR4_019: data volume in VR4 0.198 Gibit.""\
140    ),
141    command(7,
142        SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
143        NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToMM2VR4_019: SP_MODE_6_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_6_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_6_STEP_ALFA
to perform 64 scan mirror steps"\,
144        VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,26,27,28,-288000,-4500,4500)
145    ),
146    command(8,
147        SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,

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148     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToMM2VR4_019: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,66
        frame,16 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.7s VIS=13.0s"\,
149     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",16,65,35,312,650,5,66,"IR_VIS", "ALL_SUBFRAMES", "ON",6, "NO_VI
150     ),
151     command(9,
152     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
153     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
154     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToMM2VR4_019: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
155     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
156     ),
157     command(10,
158     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:18:12\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
159     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToMM2VR4_019: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
160     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
161     ),
162     note(3,
163     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
164     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToMM2VR4_019: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.230 Gibit"\
165     ),
166     command(11,
167     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
168     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToMM2VR4_019: begin data dumping into VR4.""\,
169     VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
170     ),
171     command(12,
172     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:08:40\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
173     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToMM2VR4_019: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
174     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
175     ),
176     note(4,
177     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
178     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToMM2VR4_019: data volume in VR4 0.270 Gibit.""\
179     ),
180     command(13,
181     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
182     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToMM2VR4_019: SP_MODE_6_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_6_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_6_STEP_ALFA
        to perform 64 scan mirror steps"\,
183     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,26,27,28,0,283500,4500)
184     ),
185     command(14,
186     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
187     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToMM2VR4_019: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,66
        frame,16 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.7s VIS=13.0s"\,
188     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",16,65,35,312,650,5,66,"IR_VIS", "ALL_SUBFRAMES", "ON",6, "NO_VI
189     ),
190     command(15,
191     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
192     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
193     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToMM2VR4_019: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
194     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
195     ),
196     command(16,
197     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:18:12\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
198     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToMM2VR4_019: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
199     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
200     ),

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201     note(5,
202         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
203         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToMM2VR4_019: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.230 Gibit"\
204     ),
205     command(17,
206         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
207         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToMM2VR4_019: begin data dumping into VR4."\,
208         VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
209     ),
210     command(18,
211         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:08:40\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
212         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToMM2VR4_019: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
213         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
214     ),
215     note(6,
216         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
217         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToMM2VR4_019: data volume in VR4 0.342 Gibit."\
218     ),
219     command(19,
220         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
221         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToMM2VR4_019: SP_MODE_6_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_6_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_6_STEP_ALFA
222         to perform 64 scan mirror steps"\,
223         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,26,27,28,288000,571500,4500)
224     ),
225     command(20,
226         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
227         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToMM2VR4_019: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,66
228         frame,16 RepTime,Integratation time IR=0.7s VIS=13.0s"\,
229         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",16,65,35,312,650,5,66,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",6,"NO_VI
230     ),
231     command(21,
232         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
233         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
234         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToMM2VR4_019: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
235         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
236     ),
237     command(22,
238         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:18:12\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
239         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToMM2VR4_019: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
240         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
241     ),
242     note(7,
243         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
244         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToMM2VR4_019: Cube N.7 Data Volume in MM 0.230 Gibit"\
245     ),
246     command(23,
247         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
248         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToMM2VR4_019: begin data dumping into VR4."\,
249         VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
250     ),
251     command(24,
252         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:06:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
253         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToMM2VR4_019: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
254         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
255     ),
256     note(8,
257         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,

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256     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToMM2VR4_019: data volume in VR4 0.399 Gibit."\  

257   ),  

258 end;  

259  

260 request(VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_019,  

261     START_TIME,VSA_OPNAV_019+01:47:40,  

262     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",  

263     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  

264     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  

265     KEY, "No_Key")  

266  

267     command(1,  

268     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  

269     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_019: SP_MODE_6_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_6_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_6_STEP_ALFA to  

perform 64 scan mirror steps"\  

270     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,26,27,28,-576000,-292500,4500)  

271   ),  

272     command(2,  

273     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  

274     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_019: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,66 frame,16  

RepTime,Integration time IR=0.7s VIS=13.0s"\  

275     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",16,65,35,312,650,5,66,"IR_VIS", "ALL_SUBFRAMES", "ON",6, "NO_VI  

276   ),  

277     command(3,  

278     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  

279     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\  

280     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_019: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\  

281     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  

282   ),  

283     command(4,  

284     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:18:12\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  

285     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_019: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  

286     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  

287   ),  

288     note(1,  

289     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  

290     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_019: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.661 Gibit"\  

291   ),  

292     command(5,  

293     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  

294     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_019: SP_MODE_6_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_6_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_6_STEP_ALFA to  

perform 64 scan mirror steps"\  

295     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,26,27,28,-288000,-4500,4500)  

296   ),  

297     command(6,  

298     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  

299     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_019: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,66 frame,16  

RepTime,Integration time IR=0.7s VIS=13.0s"\  

300     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",16,65,35,312,650,5,66,"IR_VIS", "ALL_SUBFRAMES", "ON",6, "NO_VI  

301   ),  

302     command(7,  

303     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  

304     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\  

305     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_019: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\  

306     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  

307   ),

```

```

308     command(8,
309         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:18:12\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
310         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_019: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
311         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
312     ),
313     note(2,
314         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
315         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_019: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.890 Gibit"\\
316     ),
317     command(9,
318         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
319         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_019: SP_MODE_6_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_6_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_6_STEP_ALFA to
320         perform 64 scan mirror steps"\\,
321         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,26,27,28,0,283500,4500)
322     ),
323     command(10,
324         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
325         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_019: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,66 frame,16
326         RepTime,Integration time IR=0.7s VIS=13.0s"\\,
327         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",16,65,35,312,650,5,66,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",6,"NO_VI
328     ),
329     command(11,
330         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
331         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\\,
332         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_019: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,
333         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
334     ),
335     command(12,
336         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:18:12\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
337         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_019: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
338         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
339     ),
340     note(3,
341         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
342         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_019: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 1.120 Gibit"\\
343     ),
344     command(13,
345         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
346         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_019: SP_MODE_6_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_6_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_6_STEP_ALFA to
347         perform 64 scan mirror steps"\\,
348         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,26,27,28,288000,571500,4500)
349     ),
350     command(14,
351         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
352         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_019: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,66 frame,16
353         RepTime,Integration time IR=0.7s VIS=13.0s"\\,
354         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",16,65,35,312,650,5,66,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",6,"NO_VI
355     ),
356     command(15,
357         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
358         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\\,
359         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_019: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,
360         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
361     ),
362     command(16,
363         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:18:12\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
  
```

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360     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_019: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.",\,
361     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
362   ),
363   note(4,
364     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
365     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVIR_019: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 1.350 Gibit"\
366   ),
367 end;
368
369 request(VIR_VSA_CloseCover_019,
370   START_TIME,VSA_OPNAV_019+03:01:31,
371   TITLE, "VIR close cover",
372   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
373   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
374   KEY, "No_Key")
375
376   command(1,
377     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
378     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CloseCover_019: Set for closing the cover.",\,
379     VIR_TC_COVER("CLOSECOVER")
380   ),
381   note(1,
382     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
383     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_CloseCover_019: Cover is closed."\<
384   ),
385 end;
386
387 request(VIR_VSA_DumpDataToVR4_019,
388   START_TIME,VSA_OPNAV_019+06:10:00,
389   TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
390   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
391   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
392   KEY, "No_Key")
393
394   command(1,
395     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
396     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_DumpDataToVR4_019: begin data dumping into VR4.",\,
397     VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
398   ),
399   command(2,
400     SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:19:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
401     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_DumpDataToVR4_019: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.",\,
402     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
403   ),
404   note(1,
405     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
406     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_DumpDataToVR4_019: data volume in VR4 1.561 Gibit."\<
407   ),
408 end;
409
410 $$EOF

```

The following SASF files were processed:

7.4 The sequence: vir_vsa_RC_003a.r00.sasf

```

1  CCSD3ZF0000100000001NJPL3KS0L015$$MARK$$;
2  MISSION_NAME = DAWN;

```

sasf

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3  SPACECRAFT_NAME = DAWN;
4  DATA_SET_ID = SPACECRAFT_ACTIVITY_SEQUENCE_DSC;
5  FILE_NAME = vir_vsa_RC_003a.r08.sasf;
6  APPLICABLE_START_TIME = 2011-196T00:00:00.000;
7  APPLICABLE_STOP_TIME = 2011-210T20:00:00.000;
8  PRODUCT_CREATION_TIME = 2011-187T08:46:48.000;
9  PRODUCER_ID = VIRTEAM;
10 SEQ_ID = vir_vsa_RC_003a.r08;
11 HOST_ID = dawndsc2;
12 CCSD3RE00000$MARK$NJPL3IF0M01300000001;
13 $$DWN      SPACECRAFT ACTIVITY SEQUENCE FILE
14 *****
15 *PROJECT   DWN
16 *SPACECRAFT 203
17 *OPERATOR  sfonte
18 *FILE_CMPLT TRUE
19 *DATE      Wed Jul 06 08:46:48 2011
20 *SEQGEN    V29.5.2 Thu Nov 29 13:34:23 PST 2007
21 *BEGIN     2011-196T00:00:00.000
22 *CUTOFF    2011-210T20:00:00.000
23 *TITLE     VIR_VSA_RC_003a_da004
24 *EPOCHS_DEF
25 *VSA_RC_003, 2011-205T06:45:00.000
26 *EPOCHS_END
27 *Input files used:
28 *File Type Last modified      File name
29 *****
30 $$EOH
31 $$EOD
32 request(VIR_VSA_RC3FullCalibNoCooling_001,
33         START_TIME,VSA_RC_003-00:45:00,
34         TITLE, "VIR full calibration sequence",
35         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
36         PROCESSOR, "GSCI",
37         KEY, "No_Key")
38
39     command(1,
40         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
41         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3FullCalibNoCooling_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY"\,
42         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
43     ),
44     command(2,
45         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
46         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3FullCalibNoCooling_001: perform the internal full calibration"\,
47         VIR_CALIBRATION("H_SPE_H_SPA_F", "CLOSECOVERATEND", "FULLCALSEQ")
48     ),
49     command(3,
50         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:15:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
51         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3FullCalibNoCooling_001: begin data dumping into VR4."\",
52         VIR_MM_DUMP("NO_COMPRESSION")
53     ),
54     command(4,
55         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:15:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
56         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3FullCalibNoCooling_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY"\,
57         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
58     ),
59     note(1,

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60     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
61     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3FullCalibNoCooling_001: full calibration is finished.\"\
62   ),
63   note(2,
64     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
65     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3FullCalibNoCooling_001: Data Volume in VR4: 0.126 Gibit,120 pages, 15960
66     packets.\"\
67   ),
68   end;
69   request(VIR_VSA_RC30penCover_001,
70     START_TIME,VSA_RC_003-00:02:00,
71     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
72     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
73     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
74     KEY, "No_Key")
75
76   command(1,
77     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
78     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC30penCover_001: Set for opening the cover.\"",
79     VIR_TC_COVER("OPENCOVER")
80   ),
81   note(1,
82     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
83     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC30penCover_001: Cover is open.\"\
84   ),
85   end;
86
87   request(VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToMM2VR4_001,
88     START_TIME,VSA_RC_003+00:00:30,
89     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, directly Virtual Recorder storing.",
90     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
91     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
92     KEY, "No_Key")
93
94   command(1,
95     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
96     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToMM2VR4_001: SP_MODE_6_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_6_END_ALFA,
97     SP_MODE_6_STEP_ALFA to perform 58 scan mirror steps\"",
98     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,26,27,28,-576000,-319500,4500)
99   ),
100  command(2,
101    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
102    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToMM2VR4_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,60
103    frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.5s VIS=12.0s\"",
104    VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,59,25,292,600,5,60,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",6,"NO_VI
105  ),
106  command(3,
107    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
108    COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556\"",
109    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToMM2VR4_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"",
110    VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
111  ),
112  command(4,
113    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:15:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
114    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToMM2VR4_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"",
115    VIR_TC_STAND_BY()

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114     ),
115     note(1,
116         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
117         TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToMM2VR4_001: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.209 Gibit"\
118     ),
119     command(5,
120         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
121         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToMM2VR4_001: begin data dumping into VR4."\",
122         VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
123     ),
124     command(6,
125         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:11:10\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
126         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToMM2VR4_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
127         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
128     ),
129     note(2,
130         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
131         TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToMM2VR4_001: data volume in VR4 0.219 Gibit."\"
132     ),
133     command(7,
134         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
135         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToMM2VR4_001: SP_MODE_6_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_6_END_ALFA,
136         SP_MODE_6_STEP_ALFA to perform 58 scan mirror steps"\",
137         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,26,27,28,-315000,-58500,4500)
138     ),
139     command(8,
140         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
141         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToMM2VR4_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,60
142         frame,15 RepTime,Integratoin time IR=0.5s VIS=12.0s"\",
143         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,59,25,292,600,5,60,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",6,"NO_VI
144     ),
145     command(9,
146         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
147         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\",
148         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToMM2VR4_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\",
149         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
150     ),
151     command(10,
152         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:15:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
153         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToMM2VR4_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
154         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
155     ),
156     note(3,
157         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
158         TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToMM2VR4_001: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.209 Gibit"\
159     ),
160     command(11,
161         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
162         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToMM2VR4_001: begin data dumping into VR4."\",
163         VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
164     ),
165     command(12,
166         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:11:10\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
167         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToMM2VR4_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
168         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
169     ),
170     note(4,

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169     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
170     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToMM2VR4_001: data volume in VR4 0.311 Gibit."\\
171   ),
172   command(13,
173     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
174     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToMM2VR4_001: SP_MODE_6_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_6_END_ALFA,
175     SP_MODE_6_STEP_ALFA to perform 58 scan mirror steps"\\,
176     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,26,27,28,-54000,202500,4500)
177   ),
178   command(14,
179     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
180     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToMM2VR4_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,60
181     frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.7s VIS=12.0s"\\,
182     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,59,35,287,600,5,60,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",6,"NO_VI
183   ),
184   command(15,
185     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
186     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\\,
187     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToMM2VR4_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,
188     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
189   ),
190   command(16,
191     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:15:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
192     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToMM2VR4_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
193     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
194   ),
195   note(5,
196     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
197     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToMM2VR4_001: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.209 Gibit"\\
198   ),
199   command(17,
200     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
201     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToMM2VR4_001: begin data dumping into VR4."\\,
202     VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
203   ),
204   command(18,
205     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:11:10\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
206     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToMM2VR4_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
207     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
208   ),
209   note(6,
210     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
211     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToMM2VR4_001: data volume in VR4 0.404 Gibit."\\
212   ),
213   command(19,
214     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
215     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToMM2VR4_001: SP_MODE_6_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_6_END_ALFA,
216     SP_MODE_6_STEP_ALFA to perform 58 scan mirror steps"\\,
217     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,26,27,28,207000,463500,4500)
218   ),
219   command(20,
220     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
221     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToMM2VR4_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,60
222     frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.7s VIS=12.0s"\\,
223     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,59,35,287,600,5,60,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",6,"NO_VI
  
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221     command(21,
222         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
223         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
224         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToMM2VR4_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
225         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
226     ),
227     command(22,
228         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:15:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
229         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToMM2VR4_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
230         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
231     ),
232     note(7,
233         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
234         TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToMM2VR4_001: Cube N.7 Data Volume in MM 0.209 Gibit"\
235     ),
236     command(23,
237         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
238         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToMM2VR4_001: begin data dumping into VR4.""\,
239         VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
240     ),
241     command(24,
242         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:11:10\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
243         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToMM2VR4_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
244         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
245     ),
246     note(8,
247         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
248         TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToMM2VR4_001: data volume in VR4 0.497 Gibit.""\
249     ),
250 end;
251
252 request(VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_002,
253     START_TIME,VSA_RC_003+02:05:30,
254     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
255     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
256     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
257     KEY, "No_Key")
258
259     command(1,
260         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
261         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_002: SP_MODE_6_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_6_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_6_STEP_ALFA
to perform 58 scan mirror steps"\,
262         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,26,27,28,-576000,-319500,4500)
263     ),
264     command(2,
265         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
266         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,60
frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.5s VIS=12.0s"\,
267         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,59,25,292,600,5,60,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",6,"NO_VI
268     ),
269     command(3,
270         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
271         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
272         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
273         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
274     ),
275     command(4,

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276     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:15:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
277     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
278     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
279   ),
280   note(1,
281     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
282     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_002: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.397 Gibit\"\\
283   ),
284   command(5,
285     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
286     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_002: SP_MODE_6_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_6_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_6_STEP_ALFA
287     to perform 58 scan mirror steps\"\\,
288     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,26,27,28,-315000,-58500,4500)
289   ),
290   command(6,
291     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
292     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,60
293     frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.5s VIS=12.0s\"\\,
294     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,59,25,292,600,5,60,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",6,"NO_VI
295   ),
296   command(7,
297     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
298     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556\"\\,
299     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
300     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
301   ),
302   command(8,
303     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:15:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
304     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
305     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
306   ),
307   note(2,
308     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
309     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_002: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.606 Gibit\"\\
310   ),
311   command(9,
312     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
313     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_002: SP_MODE_6_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_6_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_6_STEP_ALFA
314     to perform 58 scan mirror steps\"\\,
315     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,26,27,28,-54000,202500,4500)
316   ),
317   command(10,
318     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
319     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,60
320     frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.7s VIS=12.0s\"\\,
321     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,59,35,287,600,5,60,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",6,"NO_VI
322   ),
323   command(11,
324     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
325     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556\"\\,
326     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
327     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
328   ),
329   command(12,
330     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:15:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
331     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,

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328     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
329   ),
330   note(3,
331     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
332     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_002: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.815 Gibit"\
333   ),
334   command(13,
335     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
336     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_002: SP_MODE_6_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_6_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_6_STEP_ALFA
337     to perform 58 scan mirror steps"\,
338     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,26,27,28,207000,463500,4500)
339   ),
340   command(14,
341     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
342     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,60
343     frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.7s VIS=12.0s"\,
344     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,59,35,287,600,5,60,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",6,"NO_VI
345   ),
346   command(15,
347     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
348     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
349     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
350     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
351   ),
352   command(16,
353     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:15:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
354     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
355     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
356   ),
357   note(4,
358     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
359     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_002: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 1.024 Gibit"\
360   ),
361 end;
362 request(VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_003,
363   START_TIME,VSA_RC_003+04:10:30,
364   TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
365   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
366   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
367   KEY, "No_Key")
368   command(1,
369     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
370     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_003: SP_MODE_6_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_6_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_6_STEP_ALFA
371     to perform 58 scan mirror steps"\,
372     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,26,27,28,-576000,-319500,4500)
373   ),
374   command(2,
375     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
376     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,60
377     frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.5s VIS=12.0s"\,
378     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,59,25,292,600,5,60,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",6,"NO_VI
379   ),
380   command(3,
381     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,

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380     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556\"\\,
381     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
382     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
383   ),
384   command(4,
385     SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:15:36\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
386     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
387     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
388   ),
389   note(1,
390     SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:05\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
391     TEXT,\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_003: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 1.232 Gibit\"\\
392   ),
393   command(5,
394     SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:01\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
395     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_003: SP_MODE_6_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_6_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_6_STEP_ALFA
396     to perform 58 scan mirror steps\"\\,
397     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,26,27,28,-315000,-58500,4500)
398   ),
399   command(6,
400     SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:05\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
401     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,60
402     frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.5s VIS=12.0s\"\\,
403     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",15,59,25,292,600,5,60,\"IR_VIS\", \"ALL_SUBFRAMES\", \"ON\",6,\"NO_VI
404   ),
405   command(7,
406     SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:05\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
407     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556\"\\,
408     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
409     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
410   ),
411   command(8,
412     SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:15:36\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
413     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
414     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
415   ),
416   note(2,
417     SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:05\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
418     TEXT,\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_003: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 1.441 Gibit\"\\
419   ),
420   command(9,
421     SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:01\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
422     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_003: SP_MODE_6_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_6_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_6_STEP_ALFA
423     to perform 58 scan mirror steps\"\\,
424     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,26,27,28,-54000,202500,4500)
425   ),
426   command(10,
427     SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:05\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
428     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,60
429     frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.7s VIS=12.0s\"\\,
430     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",15,59,35,287,600,5,60,\"IR_VIS\", \"ALL_SUBFRAMES\", \"ON\",6,\"NO_VI
431   ),
432   command(11,
433     SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:05\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
434     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556\"\\,
435     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,

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432     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
433   ),
434   command(12,
435     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:15:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
436     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
437     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
438   ),
439   note(3,
440     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
441     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_003: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 1.650 Gibit\"
442   ),
443   command(13,
444     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
445     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_003: SP_MODE_6_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_6_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_6_STEP_ALFA
446     to perform 58 scan mirror steps\"\",
447     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,26,27,28,207000,463500,4500)
448   ),
449   command(14,
450     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
451     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,60
452     frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.7s VIS=12.0s\"\",
453     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,59,35,287,600,5,60,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",6,"NO_VI
454   ),
455   command(15,
456     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
457     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556\"\",
458     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\",
459     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
460   ),
461   command(16,
462     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:15:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
463     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
464     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
465   ),
466   note(4,
467     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
468     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3CubeToVIR_003: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 1.859 Gibit\"
469   ),
470 end;
471 request(VIR_VSA_RC3CloseCover_001,
472   START_TIME,VSA_RC_003+05:25:30,
473   TITLE, "VIR close cover",
474   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
475   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
476   KEY, "No_Key")
477 command(1,
478   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
479   NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3CloseCover_001: Set for closing the cover."\",
480   VIR_TC_COVER("CLOSECOVER")
481 ),
482 note(1,
483   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
484   TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3CloseCover_001: Cover is closed.\"
485 ),
486 end;

```

```

487
488 request(VIR_VSA_RC3CryocoolerOff_001,
489     START_TIME,VSA_RC_003+05:26:30,
490     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",
491     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
492     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
493     KEY, "No_Key")
494
495     command(1,
496     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
497     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3CryocoolerOff_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
498     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
499     ),
500     command(2,
501     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
502     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3CryocoolerOff_001: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime."\,
503     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)
504     ),
505     note(1,
506     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
507     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3CryocoolerOff_001: the cryocooling is off."\
508     ),
509 end;
510
511 request(VIR_VSA_RC3DumpDataToVR4_002,
512     START_TIME,VSA_RC_003+08:20:00,
513     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
514     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
515     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
516     KEY, "No_Key")
517
518     command(1,
519     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
520     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3DumpDataToVR4_002: begin data dumping into VR4."\,
521     VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
522     ),
523     command(2,
524     SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:39:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
525     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3DumpDataToVR4_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
526     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
527     ),
528     note(1,
529     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
530     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3DumpDataToVR4_002: data volume in VR4 1.825 Gibit."\
531     ),
532 end;
533
534 $$EOF

```

The following SASF files were processed:

7.5 The sequence: vir_vsa_RC_003b.r06.sasf

```

1  CCSD3ZF0000100000001NJPL3KS0L015$$MARK$$;
2  MISSION_NAME = DAWN;
3  SPACECRAFT_NAME = DAWN;
4  DATA_SET_ID = SPACECRAFT_ACTIVITY_SEQUENCE_DSC;
5  FILE_NAME = vir_vsa_RC_003b.r06.sasf;

```

```

6  APPLICABLE_START_TIME = 2011-196T00:00:00.000;
7  APPLICABLE_STOP_TIME = 2011-210T20:00:00.000;
8  PRODUCT_CREATION_TIME = 2011-187T09:03:07.000;
9  PRODUCER_ID = VIRTEAM;
10 SEQ_ID = vir_vsa_rc_003b.r06;
11 HOST_ID = dawndsc2;
12 CCSD3RE00000$$MARK$$NJPL3IF0M01300000001;
13 $$DWN      SPACECRAFT ACTIVITY SEQUENCE FILE
14 *****
15 *PROJECT    DWN
16 *SPACECRAFT 203
17 *OPERATOR   sfonte
18 *FILE_CMPLT TRUE
19 *DATE       Wed Jul 06 09:03:07 2011
20 *SEQGEN     V29.5.2 Thu Nov 29 13:34:23 PST 2007
21 *BEGIN      2011-196T00:00:00.000
22 *CUTOFF     2011-210T20:00:00.000
23 *TITLE      VIR_VSA_RC_003b_da004
24 *EPOCHS_DEF
25 *VSA_RC_003, 2011-205T06:45:00.000
26 *EPOCHS_END
27 *Input files used:
28 *File Type  Last modified          File name
29 *****
30 $$EOH
31 $$EOD
32 request(VIR_VSA_RC3bFullCalibration_001,
33         START_TIME,VSA_RC_003+11:00:00,
34         TITLE, "VIR cooldown and full calibration sequence",
35         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
36         PROCESSOR, "GSCI",
37         KEY, "No_Key")
38
39 spawn(1,
40       SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
41       REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
42       RT_on_board_block(vcfl_vir_calibration_full)
43     ),
44     command(1,
45             SCHEDULED_TIME,\03:30:10\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
46             NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bFullCalibration_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY"\,
47             VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
48           ),
49     note(1,
50         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
51         TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bFullCalibration_001: Full Calibration VML is finished."\
52       ),
53     note(2,
54         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
55         TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bFullCalibration_001: Data Volume in VR4: 0.126 Gibit,120 pages, 15960
56         packets."\
57       ),
58     end;
59 request(VIR_VSA_RC3bConfigMemory6Gb_001,
60         START_TIME,VSA_RC_003+14:34:01,
61         TITLE, "VIR Mass Memory setting to 6 Gibit",

```

```

62     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
63     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
64     KEY, "No_Key")
65
66     command(1,
67     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
68     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bConfigMemory6Gb_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY"\,
69     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
70     ),
71     command(2,
72     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
73     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bConfigMemory6Gb_001: changing of MM mode into MM_NOTPROTECTED_FULL (6
74     Gibit)"\,
75     VIR_TC_MM_CONF("MM_NOTPROTECTED_FULL")
76     ),
77     command(3,
78     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
79     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bConfigMemory6Gb_001: conformation of last
80     VIR_TC_MM_CONF(MM_NOTPROTECTED_FULL)"\,
81     VIR_TC_CONFIRM(54)
82     ),
83     note(1,
84     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
85     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bConfigMemory6Gb_001: VIR Mass Memory Mode is 6 Gibit not protected."
86     ),
87     end;
88
89     request(VIR_VSA_RC3bOpenCover_001,
90     START_TIME,VSA_RC_003+14:35:00,
91     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
92     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
93     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
94     KEY, "No_Key")
95
96     command(1,
97     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
98     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bOpenCover_001: Set for opening the cover."
99     VIR_TC_COVER("OPENCOVER")
100    ),
101    note(1,
102    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
103    TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bOpenCover_001: Cover is open."
104    ),
105    end;
106
107    request(VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_001,
108    START_TIME,VSA_RC_003+14:36:00,
109    TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
110    REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
111    PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
112    KEY, "No_Key")
113
114    command(1,
115    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
116    NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,60
117    frame,12 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.4s VIS=9.0s"
118    VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",12,59,20,220,450,5,60,"IR_VIS", "ALL_SUBFRAMES", "ON",10,"NO_V

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116     ),
117     command(2,
118         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
119         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
120         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
121         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
122     ),
123     command(3,
124         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:12:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
125         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
126         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
127     ),
128     note(1,
129         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
130         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_001: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.209 Gibit"\
131     ),
132     command(4,
133         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
134         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,60
135         frame,12 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.4s VIS=9.0s"\,
136         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",12,59,20,220,450,5,60,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_V
137     ),
138     command(5,
139         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
140         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
141         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
142         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
143     ),
144     command(6,
145         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:12:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
146         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
147         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
148     ),
149     note(2,
150         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
151         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_001: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.417 Gibit"\
152     ),
153     command(7,
154         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
155         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,60
156         frame,12 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.4s VIS=9.0s"\,
157         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",12,59,20,220,450,5,60,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_V
158     ),
159     command(8,
160         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
161         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
162         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
163         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
164     ),
165     command(9,
166         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:12:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
167         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
168         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
169     ),
170     note(3,
171         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,

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170     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_001: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.626 Gibit"\
171   ),
172   command(10,
173     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
174     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,60
175     frame,12 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.4s VIS=9.0s"\,
176     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",12,59,20,220,450,5,60,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_V
177   ),
178   command(11,
179     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
180     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
181     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
182     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
183   ),
184   command(12,
185     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:12:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
186     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
187     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
188   ),
189   note(4,
190     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
191     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_001: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.835 Gibit"\
192   ),
193 end;
194 request(VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_002,
195   START_TIME,VSA_RC_003+15:31:30,
196   TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
197   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
198   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
199   KEY, "No_Key")
200
201   command(1,
202     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
203     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,60
204     frame,12 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.4s VIS=9.0s"\,
205     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",12,59,20,220,450,5,60,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_V
206   ),
207   command(2,
208     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
209     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
210     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
211     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
212   ),
213   command(3,
214     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:12:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
215     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
216     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
217   ),
218   note(1,
219     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
220     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_002: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 1.044 Gibit"\
221   ),
222   command(4,
223     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,

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223 NTEXT,\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,60
    frame,12 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.4s VIS=9.0s\",
224 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",12,59,20,220,450,5,60,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_V
225 ),
226 command(5,
227 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
228 COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556\",
229 NTEXT,\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\",
230 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
231 ),
232 command(6,
233 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:12:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
234 NTEXT,\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\",
235 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
236 ),
237 note(2,
238 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
239 TEXT,\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_002: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 1.252 Gibit\"
240 ),
241 command(7,
242 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
243 NTEXT,\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,60
    frame,12 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.4s VIS=9.0s\",
244 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",12,59,20,220,450,5,60,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_V
245 ),
246 command(8,
247 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
248 COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556\",
249 NTEXT,\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\",
250 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
251 ),
252 command(9,
253 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:12:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
254 NTEXT,\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\",
255 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
256 ),
257 note(3,
258 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
259 TEXT,\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_002: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 1.461 Gibit\"
260 ),
261 command(10,
262 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
263 NTEXT,\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,60
    frame,12 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.4s VIS=9.0s\",
264 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",12,59,20,220,450,5,60,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_V
265 ),
266 command(11,
267 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
268 COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556\",
269 NTEXT,\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\",
270 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
271 ),
272 command(12,
273 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:12:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
274 NTEXT,\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\",

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275     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
276   ),
277   note(4,
278     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
279     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_002: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 1.670 Gibit\"\\
280   ),
281 end;
282
283 request(VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_003,
284   START_TIME,VSA_RC_003+16:27:00,
285   TITLE, \"VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.\",
286   REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
287   PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
288   KEY, \"No_Key\")
289
290   command(1,
291     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
292     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,60
293     frame,12 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.4s VIS=9.0s\"\\,
294     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",12,59,20,220,450,5,60,\"IR_VIS\", \"ALL_SUBFRAMES\", \"ON\",10,\"NO_V
295   ),
296   command(2,
297     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
298     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556\"\\,
299     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
300     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
301   ),
302   command(3,
303     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:12:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
304     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
305     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
306   ),
307   note(1,
308     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
309     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_003: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 1.879 Gibit\"\\
310   ),
311   command(4,
312     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
313     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,60
314     frame,12 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.4s VIS=9.0s\"\\,
315     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",12,59,20,220,450,5,60,\"IR_VIS\", \"ALL_SUBFRAMES\", \"ON\",10,\"NO_V
316   ),
317   command(5,
318     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
319     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556\"\\,
320     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
321     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
322   ),
323   command(6,
324     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:12:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
325     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
326     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
327   ),
328   note(2,
329     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
330     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_003: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 2.087 Gibit\"\\

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329     ),
330     command(7,
331         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
332         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,60
frame,12 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.4s VIS=9.0s"\,
333         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",12,59,20,220,450,5,60,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_V
334     ),
335     command(8,
336         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
337         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
338         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
339         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
340     ),
341     command(9,
342         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:12:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
343         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
344         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
345     ),
346     note(3,
347         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
348         TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_003: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 2.296 Gibit"\
349     ),
350     command(10,
351         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
352         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,60
frame,12 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.4s VIS=9.0s"\,
353         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",12,59,20,220,450,5,60,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_V
354     ),
355     command(11,
356         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
357         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
358         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
359         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
360     ),
361     command(12,
362         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:12:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
363         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
364         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
365     ),
366     note(4,
367         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
368         TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_003: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 2.505 Gibit"\
369     ),
370 end;
371
372 request(VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_004,
373     START_TIME,VSA_RC_003+17:22:30,
374     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
375     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
376     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
377     KEY, "No_Key")
378
379     command(1,
380         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
381         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,60
frame,12 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.4s VIS=9.0s"\,

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382     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",12,59,20,220,450,5,60,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_V
383 ),
384     command(2,
385     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
386     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
387     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
388     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
389 ),
390     command(3,
391     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:12:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
392     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
393     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
394 ),
395     note(1,
396     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
397     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_004: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 2.714 Gibit"\
398 ),
399     command(4,
400     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
401     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,60
frame,12 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.4s VIS=9.0s"\,
402     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",12,59,20,220,450,5,60,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_V
403 ),
404     command(5,
405     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
406     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
407     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
408     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
409 ),
410     command(6,
411     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:12:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
412     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
413     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
414 ),
415     note(2,
416     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
417     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_004: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 2.922 Gibit"\
418 ),
419     command(7,
420     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
421     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,60
frame,12 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.4s VIS=9.0s"\,
422     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",12,59,20,220,450,5,60,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_V
423 ),
424     command(8,
425     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
426     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
427     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
428     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
429 ),
430     command(9,
431     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:12:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
432     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
433     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
434 ),

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435     note(3,
436         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
437         TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_004: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 3.131 Gibit"\
438     ),
439     command(10,
440         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
441         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,60
         frame,12 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.4s VIS=9.0s"\,
442         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",12,59,20,220,450,5,60,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_V
443     ),
444     command(11,
445         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
446         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
447         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
448         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
449     ),
450     command(12,
451         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:12:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
452         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
453         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
454     ),
455     note(4,
456         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
457         TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_004: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 3.340 Gibit"\
458     ),
459 end;
460
461 request(VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_005,
462     START_TIME,VSA_RC_003+18:18:00,
463     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
464     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
465     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
466     KEY, "No_Key")
467
468     command(1,
469         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
470         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_005: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,60
         frame,12 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.4s VIS=9.0s"\,
471         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",12,59,20,220,450,5,60,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_V
472     ),
473     command(2,
474         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
475         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
476         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_005: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
477         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
478     ),
479     command(3,
480         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:12:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
481         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_005: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
482         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
483     ),
484     note(1,
485         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
486         TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_005: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 3.549 Gibit"\
487     ),
488     command(4,

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489     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
490     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_005: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,60
         frame,12 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.4s VIS=9.0s"\,
491     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",12,59,20,220,450,5,60,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_V
492     ),
493     command(5,
494     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
495     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
496     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_005: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
497     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
498     ),
499     command(6,
500     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:12:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
501     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_005: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
502     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
503     ),
504     note(2,
505     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
506     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_005: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 3.757 Gibit"\
507     ),
508     command(7,
509     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
510     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_005: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,60
         frame,12 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.4s VIS=9.0s"\,
511     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",12,59,20,220,450,5,60,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_V
512     ),
513     command(8,
514     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
515     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
516     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_005: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
517     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
518     ),
519     command(9,
520     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:12:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
521     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_005: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
522     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
523     ),
524     note(3,
525     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
526     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_005: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 3.966 Gibit"\
527     ),
528     command(10,
529     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
530     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_005: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,60
         frame,12 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.4s VIS=9.0s"\,
531     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",12,59,20,220,450,5,60,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_V
532     ),
533     command(11,
534     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
535     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
536     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_005: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
537     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
538     ),
539     command(12,
540     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:12:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,

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541     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_005: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
542     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
543   ),
544   note(4,
545     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
546     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_005: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 4.175 Gibit"\
547   ),
548   end;
549
550   request(VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_006,
551     START_TIME,VSA_RC_003+19:13:30,
552     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
553     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
554     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
555     KEY, "No_Key")
556
557   command(1,
558     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
559     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_006: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,60
frame,12 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.4s VIS=9.0s"\,
560     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",12,59,20,220,450,5,60,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_V
561   ),
562   command(2,
563     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
564     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
565     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_006: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
566     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
567   ),
568   command(3,
569     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:12:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
570     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
571     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
572   ),
573   note(1,
574     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
575     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_006: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 4.384 Gibit"\
576   ),
577   command(4,
578     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
579     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_006: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,60
frame,12 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.4s VIS=9.0s"\,
580     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",12,59,20,220,450,5,60,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_V
581   ),
582   command(5,
583     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
584     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
585     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_006: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
586     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
587   ),
588   command(6,
589     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:12:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
590     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
591     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
592   ),
593   note(2,
594     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,

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595     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_006: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 4.592 Gibit"\
596   ),
597   command(7,
598     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
599     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_006: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,60
600     frame,12 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.4s VIS=9.0s"\,
601     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",12,59,20,220,450,5,60,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_V
602   ),
603   command(8,
604     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
605     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
606     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_006: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
607     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
608   ),
609   command(9,
610     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:12:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
611     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
612     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
613   ),
614   note(3,
615     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
616     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_006: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 4.801 Gibit"\
617   ),
618   command(10,
619     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
620     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_006: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,60
621     frame,12 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.4s VIS=9.0s"\,
622     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",12,59,20,220,450,5,60,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_V
623   ),
624   command(11,
625     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
626     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=.556"\,
627     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_006: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
628     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
629   ),
630   command(12,
631     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:12:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
632     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
633     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
634   ),
635   note(4,
636     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
637     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bPushbroomToVIR_006: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 5.010 Gibit"\
638   ),
639 end;
640
641 request(VIR_VSA_RC3bCloseCover_001,
642   START_TIME,VSA_RC_003+20:09:00,
643   TITLE, "VIR close cover",
644   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
645   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
646   KEY, "No_Key")
647
648   command(1,
649     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
650     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bCloseCover_001: Set for closing the cover.""\,

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649     VIR_TC_COVER("CLOSECOVER")
650   ),
651   note(1,
652     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
653     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bCloseCover_001: Cover is closed.\"\
654   ),
655 end;
656
657 request(VIR_VSA_RC3bCryocoolerOff_001,
658   START_TIME,VSA_RC_003+20:10:00,
659   TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",
660   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
661   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
662   KEY, "No_Key")
663
664   command(1,
665     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
666     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bCryocoolerOff_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\,
667     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
668   ),
669   command(2,
670     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
671     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bCryocoolerOff_001: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime.\"\,
672     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)
673   ),
674   note(1,
675     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
676     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bCryocoolerOff_001: the cryocooling is off.\"\
677   ),
678 end;
679
680 request(VIR_VSA_RC3bDumpDataToVR4_001,
681   START_TIME,VSA_RC_003+20:11:00,
682   TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
683   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
684   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
685   KEY, "No_Key")
686
687   command(1,
688     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
689     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bDumpDataToVR4_001: begin data dumping into VR4.\"\,
690     VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
691   ),
692   command(2,
693     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:39:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
694     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bDumpDataToVR4_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\,
695     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
696   ),
697   note(1,
698     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
699     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_RC3bDumpDataToVR4_001: data volume in VR4 0.458 Gibit.\"\
700   ),
701 end;
702
703 request(VIR_VSA_RC3bDumpDataToVR4_002,
704   START_TIME,VSA_RC_003+26:35:00,
705   TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
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706     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
707     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
708     KEY, "No_Key")
709
710     command(1,
711         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
712         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bDumpDataToVR4_002: begin data dumping into VR4."\,
713         VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
714     ),
715     command(2,
716         SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:29:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
717         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bDumpDataToVR4_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
718         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
719     ),
720     note(1,
721         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
722         TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bDumpDataToVR4_002: data volume in VR4 0.873 Gibit."\
723     ),
724 end;
725
726 request(VIR_VSA_RC3bDumpDataToVR4_003,
727     START_TIME,VSA_RC_003+28:35:00,
728     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
729     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
730     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
731     KEY, "No_Key")
732
733     command(1,
734         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
735         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bDumpDataToVR4_003: begin data dumping into VR4."\,
736         VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
737     ),
738     command(2,
739         SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:29:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
740         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bDumpDataToVR4_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
741         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
742     ),
743     note(1,
744         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
745         TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bDumpDataToVR4_003: data volume in VR4 1.620 Gibit."\
746     ),
747 end;
748
749 request(VIR_VSA_RC3bDumpDataToVR4_004,
750     START_TIME,VSA_RC_003+30:35:00,
751     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
752     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
753     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
754     KEY, "No_Key")
755
756     command(1,
757         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
758         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_RC3bDumpDataToVR4_004: begin data dumping into VR4."\,
759         VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
760     ),
761     command(2,
762         SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:29:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,

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763     NTEXT, \"VIR_VSA_RC3bDumpDataToVR4_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
764     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
765   ),
766   note(1,
767     SCHEDULED_TIME, \\00:00:05\\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
768     TEXT, \"VIR_VSA_RC3bDumpDataToVR4_004: data volume in VR4 2.367 Gibit.\"\\
769   ),
770 end;
771
772 request(VIR_VSA_RC3bDumpDataToVR4_005,
773   START_TIME, VSA_RC_003+32:35:00,
774   TITLE, \"VIR dump data into VR4\",
775   REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
776   PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
777   KEY, \"No_Key\")
778
779   command(1,
780     SCHEDULED_TIME, \\00:00:00\\, FROM_REQUEST_START,
781     NTEXT, \"VIR_VSA_RC3bDumpDataToVR4_005: begin data dumping into VR4.\"\\,
782     VIR_MM_DUMP(\"LOSSLESS\")
783   ),
784   command(2,
785     SCHEDULED_TIME, \\02:29:55\\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
786     NTEXT, \"VIR_VSA_RC3bDumpDataToVR4_005: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
787     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
788   ),
789   note(1,
790     SCHEDULED_TIME, \\00:00:05\\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
791     TEXT, \"VIR_VSA_RC3bDumpDataToVR4_005: data volume in VR4 3.612 Gibit.\"\\
792   ),
793 end;
794
795 request(VIR_VSA_RC3bPowerOff_001,
796   START_TIME, VSA_RC_003+35:10:00,
797   TITLE, \"VIR Power off\",
798   REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
799   PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
800   KEY, \"No_Key\")
801
802   note(1,
803     SCHEDULED_TIME, \\00:00:00\\, FROM_REQUEST_START,
804     TEXT, \"VIR_VSA_RC3bPowerOff_001: Power off VIR instrument.\"\\
805   ),
806   spawn(1,
807     SCHEDULED_TIME, \\00:00:01\\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
808     REQ_ENGINE_ID, \\ANY_ENGINE\\,
809     RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)
810   ),
811 end;
812
813 $$EOF
```